

EDAP+ TN on GHGSat Validation

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
1.0	16/11/2023	First Version with SRON and University of Leicester work for EDAP+/WO-3
1.1	23/12/2023	Included Maturity Matrix evaluation for GHGSat
1.2	23/12/2023	Included C. Albinet comments

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1. INTRODUCTION

This technical note details the results of the preliminary data quality assessments (methane CH₄ emission rates and CH₄ abundance maps) performed on a dataset of CH₄ products generated from the GHGSat constellation.

The aforementioned data quality assessments are performed in accordance with the assessment guidelines, detailed in [RD-1, RD-2], that constitute the *European Space Agency (ESA) Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot (EDAP+)* project's *Earth Observation (EO) Mission Data Quality Assessment Framework*. An important representation of the latter framework, constructed by the *National Physical Laboratory (NPL)*, is what is known as the maturity matrix. It is a diagrammatic summary of the following:

- **Documentation Review:** the EDAP+ Atmospheric team reviews materials provided by the data provider (documentation), some of which may not be publicly available, or even the scientific community (e.g. published papers). The results are detailed in Section 2 (covering the first column of the maturity matrix, see Table 2-1).
- **Data Quality Assessments:** SRON (Netherlands Institute for Space Research) and University of Leicester performs data quality assessments (i.e. validation assessments), independently of those performed by the data provider. The results are detailed in Section 3 and Section 4 (covering the last column of the maturity matrix, see Table 2-1 and Table 2-2).

The above data quality assessments are performed by the EDAP+ team using the appropriate in-house and open-source ad-hoc scripts and tools.

It is important to note the purpose of the EDAP+ EO Mission Data Quality Assessment Framework is to ensure that the delivered commercial mission data is fit for purpose and that all decisions regarding the inclusion of the commercial mission as an ESA third party mission can be made fairly and with confidence.

REFERENCE

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, EDAP.REP.001, v2.2, 6th December 2022.
- RD-2. Earth Observation Mission Quality Assessment Framework - Atmospheric Guidelines, EDAP.REP.061, v0.1, October 2021
- RD-3. GHGSat Incorporated Satellite Imagery and Data Product Specifications, GHG-1501-7003, 21 July 2021
- RD-4. GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) for Methane Retrieval, GHG-1292-6003, 16 July 2021
- RD-5. GHGSat-C1 Ground characterization and validation, GHG-1292-1002-a, 19 July 2021
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1.1 Glossary

AOI: Area Of Interest

ATBD: Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document

CAMS: Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service

DBSCAN: Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise

GHGSat: Green House Gases Satellite

EDAP: Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot

EO: Earth Observation

E-PRTR: European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register

ESA: European Space Agency

EULA: End-User License Agreement

GEOS-FP: Goddard Earth Observing System – Forward Processing

IME: Integrated Mass Enhancement

NPL: National Physic Laboratory

TROPOMI: TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument

SRON: Netherlands Institute for Space Research

SWIR: Short Wave Infrared Spectrometer

USCB: Upper Silesian Coal Basin

WAF-P: Wide-Angle Fabry-Perot (Imaging Spectrometer)

WFMD: Weighting Function Modified Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy

WRF: Weather Research & Forecasting model

2. CAL/VAL MATURITY MATRICES

A Cal/Val maturity matrix provides a high-level colour-coded summary of the quality assessment results. The matrix contains a column for each section of analysis, and cells for each subsection of analysis. Subsection grades are indicated by the colour of the respective grid cell, which are defined in the key. A padlock symbol in the corner of given cell indicates that the information used to assess the respective subsection is not available to the public. The reporting of assessment results is divided between two Cal/Val maturity matrices, as follows:

- *Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix*
- *Detailed Validation Cal/Val Maturity Matrix*

The Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix provides an overall summary of the quality assessment results (see Table 2-1). The matrix on the left summarises the results of the Documentation Review, while the additional column on the right summarises the results of the Detailed Validation. The Validation Summary column is separated from the main table to make clear the results can come from multiple assessment sources.

2.1 SUMMARY CAL/VAL MATURITY MATRIX

This assessment aims to review mission quality as evidenced by its documentation. It is divided into the follow sections:

- Product Information
- Metrology
- Product Generation
- Validation Summary

Table 2-1 Summary Cal/Val Maturity Matrix

Table 2ta Provider Documentation Review			Validation Summary	Key	
Product Information	Metrology	Product Generation		Not Assessed	Not Assessable
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	Measurement Validation Method	Basic		
Availability & Accessibility	Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	Measurement Validation Results Compliance	Good		
Product Format, Flags & Metadata	Metrological Traceability Documentation	Geometric Validation Method	Excellent		
User Documentation	Uncertainty Characterisation	Geometric Validation Results Compliance	Ideal		
	Ancillary Data Not Public				

Data products should be accompanied with the following minimum set of documentation for users, which should be regularly updated as required:

- Product User Guide/Manual (PUG/PUM)
- Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD)

In Section 2.3 all inputs used to assess status-of-the-art of GHGSat product are listed.

Section 3 and Section 4 detail the validation activity performed by SRON and University of Leicester on Madrid landfills and Poland coal mines, respectively.

2.2 GHGSat CH4 DETAILED VALIDATION MATRIX

Table 2-2 Detailed validation matrix

GHGSat CH4 detailed validation		
Measurement	GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric for Madrid Landfills	GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric For Poland Coal Mines
	GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric Madrid Landfills Results Compliance	GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric Poland Coal Mines Results Compliance
Geometric	Geometric GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric #1 Method	Geometric GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric #2 Method
	Geometric GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric #1 Results Compliance	Geometric GHGSat vs TROPOMI Performance Metric #2 Results Compliance

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Good
Excellent
Ideal
Not Public

2.3 DATA PROVIDER DOCUMENTATION REVIEW

2.3.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Grade: Excellent	
Justification	<p>Almost all required information present in user manual [RD-2] or metadata.</p> <p>The ideal grade should be obtained adding more clearly information about product version, id and URL/DOI.</p>
Products Name	<p>Abundance Dataset – CH4</p> <p>Concentration Map – CH4</p>
Sensor Name	<p>Wide-angle Fabry-Perot (WAF-P) Imaging Spectrometer</p> <p>On board the GHGSat satellites there is also a VIS-2 imager, but products are not delivered to EDAP+ contract and assessed in this document</p>
Sensor Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2D-Optical infrared imaging spectrometer; Wavelength detection range: 1600-1700 nm in multiple bands, unpolarized. • <i>The auxiliary imager is used to obtain a high-resolution image of the ground in the 500-550 nm region.</i>
Mission Type	Constellation of 9 satellites (C-1 → C-8 + demonstrator GHGSat-D) at the time of this study
Mission Orbit	Sun-synchronous low Earth orbit with 523 km altitude, 97.5 deg inclination, 95 minutes orbital period.
Product Version Number	<p>V1 - Processor levels from metadata:</p> <p>L0, L1A, L1B, L2A processor: GHGSat-Toolchain, v9.2.0</p> <p>L2B processor: ghg.post_processing</p>
Product ID	<p>GHGSat Product numbers:</p> <p>Surface Reflectance: A.1.0</p> <p>Abundance Dataset with uncertainty and flags: A.2.0_CH4</p> <p>Concentration maps: A.3.0_CH4</p> <p>Emission Rate: D.1.0_CH4</p>
Processing level of product	L2B, L4 (Source Emission Rate)
Measured Quantity Name	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Surface Reflectance, 2. Abundance Dataset CH4, 3. Concentration Maps CH4 4. Source Emission Rate
Measured Quantity Units	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. [sr⁻¹], 2. [column average mixing ratio in ppb (parts per billion) or column density in mol/m²], 3. [ppb or mol/m²] <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. [kg/hour]
Stated Measurement Quality	Methane column density precision equal to about 2% of background

	<p>Source detection threshold equal to 100 kg/hour in 3 m/s wind (for methane)</p> <p>Geometric accuracies < 30 m</p>
Spatial Resolution	<p>Nominal ground sampling for WAF-P: 33 m</p> <p><i>Nominal ground sampling for VIS-2: 20 m</i></p>
Spatial Coverage	<p>WAF-P: Pictures with field of view of 12 km x 12 km</p> <p>Sensor pointing capability: +/- 20 degrees from nadir along & cross-track.</p> <p><i>VIS-2: Swath width 35 km</i></p>
Temporal Resolution	<p>Single satellite revisiting time: 14 days</p>
Temporal Coverage	<p>GHGSat-D Launched in June 2016. Four years minimum expected lifetime.</p> <p>GHGSat-C1 Launched in September 2020. Four years minimum expected lifetime.</p> <p>GHGSat-C2 Launched in January 2021. Four years minimum expected lifetime.</p>
Point of Contact	<p>https://www.ghgsat.com, operations@ghgsat.com</p>
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<p>https://www.ghgsat.com/en/ (mission official website)</p>
Conditions for access and use	<p>Limited by EULA Agreement. EULA file name reported in metadata (GHG-2000-2003-b_EULA_2021.pdf)</p>
Limitations on public access	<p>Limited by EULA Agreement</p>
Product Abstract	<p>The primary product of GHGSat is the map of methane column density and surface reflectance, acquired with a very high spatial resolution (less than 33 m).</p> <p>Methane column densities and surface reflectance information are retrieved for each ground pixel using a measurement model which includes surface, instrument, and atmospheric contributions to the spectral radiance. The resulting arrays are georeferenced, giving the "Surface Reflectance Image" and the "Abundance Dataset" for CH₄.</p> <p>These Level 2 products cover a domain size of approximately 12 km x 12 km. Reflectance and abundance products are then combined into the CH₄ Concentration Map.</p> <p>Abundance datasets also allow Source Emission Rate to be estimated for individual sources. Source rate is a L4 product retrieved using site information and weather data from global meteorological models or local weather stations.</p>

Availability & Accessibility		
Grade: Good		
Justification	Data meets many of the FAIR principles, but no data management plan is made available to users. Catalogue available at: https://spectra.ghgsat.com/	
Compliant with FAIR principles	To be Findable:	
	F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier	Yes
	F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)	Yes
	F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes	Yes
	F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource	Yes
	To be Accessible:	
	A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol	No
	A1.1 the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable	No
	A1.2 the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary	Yes
	A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available	No
	To be Interoperable:	
	I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.	Yes
	I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles	Yes
	I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data	No
	To be Reusable:	
	R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes	Yes
	R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license	Yes
	R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance	Yes

	R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards	Yes
Data Management Plan	Not available to users	
Availability Status	<p>The collection is open on demand for research and application development, prototype, and test projects to worldwide users.</p> <p>Data are available upon submission of a Project Proposal subject to evaluation and acceptance by ESA and the data owner.</p>	

Product Format	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Data use standard formats (with exception of Concentration maps that should be intended for a quick look of observation results) and are documented with a rich set of metadata. Metadata variables and attributes are understandable: they are named extensively using the underscore as space between words.
Product File Format	GeoTIFF for Abundance Dataset, Surface Reflectance PNG image for Concentration Maps CSV file for Source Emission Rates
Metadata Conventions	No specific convention followed
Analysis Ready Data?	No

User Documentation		
Grade: Excellent		
Justification	Product User Guide and ATBD are generally well documented with ATBD providing a detailed information of all principal processes for data analysis and retrieval, with many citations to literature. ATBD not publicly available.	
<i>Document</i>	<i>References</i>	<i>QA4ECV Compliant</i>
Product User Guide	GHGSat Incorporated Satellite Imagery and Data Product Specifications [RD-2]	No
ATBD	GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4]	Yes

2.3.2 Metrology

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Instrument characterization pre and post launch are considered fit-for-purpose and covers all the principal components and aspect of the instrument. Instrument calibration pre-flight activities are detailly described. On-flight calibration is performed through four led enlightening the SWIR camera with a controlled emission. Below a brief summarize of the ground-tests is reported.</p> <p>SWIR spectrometer uses an InGaAs camera as sensor, whose pixel are carefully calibrated, calculating offset, gain and dark current to convert the digital signal output into an incoming irradiance; non-linear response to irradiance has been considered. Pixels quantum efficiency was also tested for the correct measurement of irradiance at a given wavelength. Optical filters have been characterized observing the transmission as function of wavelength and angle of incidence.</p> <p>SWIR's Fabry-Perot has been independently tested to evaluate its performance.</p> <p>On-board calibration led and their irradiance uniformity on camera pixels has been calibrated. The calibration module contains a shutter that serves when closed to reflect the LED light towards the camera and to prevent the light from the scene to reach the sensor: the light tightness of the shutter has been tested.</p> <p>The general characteristics of SWIR have been also assessed, measuring the global scaling factor between the true spectral radiance incident on the payload and the measured signal. This transmittance factor accounts for miscellaneous losses in the optical components and is required to precisely measure the ground reflectance (albedo). Additionally, the same setup is used to measure the rejection ratio for out-of-band light.</p> <p>Optical tests have been made to evaluate SWIR spectral response, stray-light and ghosting effects.</p> <p>This grade could be raised to excellent, providing literature references of the methodology applied.</p>
References	GHGSat-C1 Ground characterization and validation [RD-5]

Geometric Calibration & Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Ground tests for geometric characterisation of the sensor are detailly described. The methodology is considered fit-for-purpose to reach the geometric accuracy stated of 1 pixel (about 30 m).</p> <p>Even the spatial distortion and field of view is tested on ground: optical components such as lenses and mirrors induce some distortion of the ground image formed in the camera plane. The maximum deviation measured is within 1 SWIR pixel.</p> <p>The auxiliary camera VIS-2 spatial resolution has been tested.</p>
References	GHGSat-C1 Ground characterization and validation [RD-5]

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	Measurement traceability chain documented from L0 to L4. The principal steps to retrieve the products are all documented in the ATBD. Principal uncertainty sources described in the ATBD and [RD-6] and added in the retrieval scheme, but no rigorous uncertainty tree diagram provided.
References	GHGSat-C1 Calibration and Validation Plan and Description of Errors, [RD-6] GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4]

Uncertainty Characterisation	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Regarding L2 uncertainty, citing the [RD-6]: “A pre-launch analysis based on subsystem specifications from suppliers, our own ground characterization results, experience with GHGSat-D and GHGSat-C1 simulations indicated a projected RMS error level of approximately 2% of background”.</p> <p>The uncertainty has been evaluated with CAL/VAL comparison and statistical analysis of retrieval outputs in scenes where no plume is present for a variety of terrain classes.</p> <p>Several sources of uncertainty have been considered: random noise, unmodelled instrument effects, unmodelled atmospheric effects such as the presence of clouds and aerosol, imperfect image registration.</p> <p>However, only the instrumental noise is rigorous treated in the retrieval algorithm and delivered in the products, underestimating the uncertainty level. An improved system is under development to report a more realistic error layer based on data properties of the specific observation and retrieval. The instrumental noise is represented with a measurement error covariance matrix. Pixels are assumed to be statistically independent and uncorrelated in time such that the measurement error covariance matrix is diagonal. Off-diagonal entries are not considered.</p> <p>As grade we propose “Good”: the systematic terms not rigorously calculated in the retrieval should play a non-negligible role on the uncertainty estimation (e.g., aerosol contribution); however, expanded comparison to measurements by other sensors has been proposed in the documentation, a limited use of GUM approach is present and uncertainty per pixel provided.</p> <p>L4 product uncertainty is estimated on the order of 52%, accounting for the principal sources of error of the integrated mass enhancement method described in Varon (2018), [RD-13].</p> <p>The presence of atmospheric and systematic terms in the L2 retrieval should fully achieve the “Good” grade and increase it to better score.</p>
References	<p>GHGSat-C1 Calibration and Validation Plan and Description of Errors, [RD-6]</p> <p>GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4]</p>

Ancillary Data	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>GHGSat retrieval algorithm employs several additional information as a-priori, described below.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Landsat-8 information is used for the albedo priori [RD-7]. • Closest-in-time time CH₄, CO₂, and H₂O values from AIRS are used for atmospheric profiles [RD-8]. • Vertical profiles for pressure, temperature and volume mixing ratios are obtained from the 1976 US Standard Atmospheric model (US National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, 1976), covering altitudes 0km to 120km (ASL) [RD-9]. • HITRAN API is used for calculating the absorption coefficients in the retrieval, assuming a Voight line-shape profile [RD-10]. • PL 2016 disk-integrated Solar Pseudo-Transmittance Spectrum [RD-11] is used in the retrieval forward model. The correct Sun emission spectra is obtained following the NRLSSI2 model [RD-12]. <p>All ancillary data are specified in the ATBD and judged fit-for-purpose; an identifier to the specific product used for each observation should be added to the metadata to improve the evaluation. Atmospheric ancillary data are used for the a-priori calculation so they impact on the retrieved products should be limited.</p>
References	<p>GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4].</p> <p>Roy, 2014, [RD-7].</p> <p>Chahine, 2006, [RD-8].</p> <p>U.S. Standard Atmosphere, 1976, [RD-9].</p> <p>Kochanov, 2016, [RD-10].</p> <p>Toon, 2014, [RD-11]</p> <p>Lean, 2010, [RD-12].</p> <p>Varon et al., 2018. [RD-13].</p>

2.3.3 Product Generation

Geometric Processing	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Instrument operates in “target” mode in which the satellite attitude is adjusted to keep the round target site in the field of view for much longer than it would if operated in nadir (downward pointing) mode, thereby increasing the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). Approximately 200 closely overlapping two-dimensional images are taken in which spectral information is superimposed over an image of the ground. Over the duration of the ~20 observation sequence, the ground target traverses the field-of-view, sampling the full extent of the spectral information contained in the images.</p> <p>The transformation between camera coordinates to ground coordinates is fully described in the ATBD. The absence of geometric quality flag does not allow to obtain higher grade.</p>
References	GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4].

Calibration Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>GHGSat-C2 performs on-flight calibration tests, or “slow frames” tests, where a series of frames are acquired at fixed illumination. There is a slow frames "dark" test in which dark frames are acquired, and a slow frames "bright" test in which the onboard four LEDs illuminate the camera at constant intensity. These tests help to evaluate the response of the camera to known sources of light and to identify damaged pixels.</p> <p>LEDs illuminate the sensor with known irradiance; their calibration is performed on-ground, characterizing LEDs irradiance and uniformity. The shutter system used for reflecting the light to the sensor is also tested on-ground before launch. Products calibration (from raw counts to radiances) employs the dark current measurements acquired before and after the observation, considering the non-linearity of the system gain. Calibration parameters per pixel are characterized with on-ground tests.</p> <p>Documentation describes both on ground tests and the algorithms leading to calibrated data.</p>
References	<p>GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4]</p> <p>GHGSat-C1 Ground characterization and validation, [RD-5]</p>

Retrieval Algorithm	
Grade: Good	
Justification	<p>Retrieval algorithm for L2 data and Emission source rate (L4) is documented with abundant citations to literature and considered fit-for-purpose.</p> <p>A deeper sensitivity analysis and some validation examples should be provided. This is suggested due to the lack in the retrieved uncertainty of the systematic errors introduced by the unmodelled effects of the aerosol and clouds. GHGSat stated precision is 2% but the aerosol contribution to the uncertainty should have the same order of magnitude. In particular at page 9 of the ATBD, we read: <i>“a 5% bias in the absolute methane column density – on the upper end of what is estimated from neglecting scattering due to aerosols, for instance (Aben et al., 2007 [RD-13]; Butz et al., 2009 [RD-15]; Houweling et al., 2005 [RD-16]) – would lead to a 5% bias in the local methane enhancement”</i>.</p> <p>The aerosol contribution to the emission rate should be less significant, due to the error structure, dominated by the wind uncertainty.</p> <p>The report of an uncertainty validation and sensitivity analysis in the mission documentation should increase the evaluation score. The mission documentation suggests that further development on this sense will be added in the future.</p>
References	<p>GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4].</p> <p>GHGSat-C1 Calibration and Validation Plan and Description of Errors, [RD-6]</p>

Mission-Specific Processing	
Grade: Not Assessable	
Justification	No additional process to L2 and L4 data is present after the retrieval.
Reference	GHGSat-C1 Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document for Methane Retrieval, [RD-4].

3. DETAILED VALIDATION – MADRID LAS DEHESAS AND PINTO LANDFILLS

The urban area of Madrid is one of the methane emission hot spots that can be detected using the Sentinel-5P TROPOMI instrument that observes methane with a resolution of $7 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$. A 2021 ESA web story attributed a large part of the observed methane plumes from the area to the Las Dehesas and Pinto landfills based on GHGSat satellite observations that, at a resolution of $25 \times 25 \text{ m}^2$, can be used to estimate facility-level emissions. This report describes a follow-up campaign analyzing TROPOMI (using both the operational product as well as the WFMD product), 10 days of GHGSat satellite data, and 2 days of GHGSat airborne data to better understand emissions from the Madrid area and its landfills.

Analysis of the enhancements seen by TROPOMI and GHGSat shows strong correlation between different days as well as significant bias between both TROPOMI products and GHGSat (as expected). This bias can be explained by the different sensitivities, footprints, and overpass times of the instruments. Emissions estimated using both TROPOMI products using different implementations of the Integrated Mass Enhancement method were consistent with each other ($14 \pm 9 \text{ t/hr}$) and are representative of urban-scale emissions beyond the two landfills. The GHGSat satellite data show average emissions rates of $2.5 \pm 1.1 \text{ t/hr}$ for Las Dehesas and $3.2 \pm 1.7 \text{ t/hr}$ for Pinto. The sum of the GHGSat aircraft plumes on the day with overlapping data was consistent with the GHGSat satellite data. These emissions are larger than reported to E-PRTR by both Las Dehesas (0.3 t/hr) and Pinto (1.6 t/hr). Based on an exchange with the Las Dehesas landfill operator, the reported emissions are a function of the assumed gas capture efficiency of the landfill. The results therefore suggest that the employed capture efficiency may be overestimated.

Finally, we find that GHGSat aircraft data can be used to find many individual sources within the landfill. Their locations are consistent with GHGSat satellite plume origins and originate from active areas of the landfill as identified based on high-resolution visual imagery from satellites and confirmed by the Las Dehesas operator. This ability also shows the large potential of using GHGSat (aircraft) data to support emission mitigation activities.

Authors of this chapter are:

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3.1 INTRODUCTION

The TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI, RD-17) is a spaceborne global methane mapper with a daily revisit frequency. Its observations feature plumes arising from the strongest methane-emitting hotspots, a third of which are related to urban areas (e.g. RD-18). In Europe, the city of Madrid appears as one of these hotspots, but the coarse resolution of TROPOMI observations does not allow to precisely identify the exact facilities responsible for these emissions. However, hotspots detected in TROPOMI observations can provide targets to satellites with a higher spatial resolution, which have the capability of zooming-in to identify the responsible facilities. This synergy between the detection capabilities of TROPOMI and the zooming capabilities of high-resolution instruments has for example been demonstrated in (RD-19; EDAP study, 2021). Following this ‘tip-and-cue’ strategy, GHGSat, a Canadian company that operates a constellation of such high-resolution satellites, was guided by TROPOMI and could observe methane plumes arising from two landfills in the Madrid urban area.

On November 10th 2021, the European Space Agency (ESA) communicated a web story reporting on this detection of methane emissions arising from two landfills near Madrid (https://www.esa.int/Applications/Observing_the_Earth/Satellites_detect_large_methane_emissions_from_Madrid_landfills). For example, *Figure 3-1* shows methane plumes observed by TROPOMI arising from the Madrid urban area on three different days.

Figure 3-1 Examples of methane emission plumes arising from southeast of the Madrid urban area, observed by TROPOMI in 2021 on August 17th (left), October 8th (center) and 14th (right). Arrows depict the 10-m wind field obtained from GEOS-FP, the black dot indicates the Madrid city center.

Following the large (local) interest in the web story, ESA organized an aircraft campaign in the summer of 2022, and a dedicated follow-up study to compare satellite- and airborne-based emission estimates in the framework of EDAP+, in order to increase the confidence in the spaceborne monitoring of methane-emitting hotspots near Madrid. This Technical Note (TN) presents the results of this study.

3.2 MEASUREMENTS

This section will describe the TROPOMI measurements, including the two different methane retrieval products used in the study, and the GHGSat satellite and aircraft observations.

3.2.1 TROPOMI measurements

The TROPOspheric Monitoring Instrument (TROPOMI), jointly developed by ESA and the Netherlands Space Office, is flying on-board the Sentinel-5 Precursor satellite, which was put on its sun-synchronous orbit in late 2017. It measures back-scattered sunlight in (a.o.) the near and short-wave infrared (NIR and SWIR, resp.) around 0.76 and 2.3 μm (resp.), at a moderate 5.5x7 km² spatial resolution and with a daily global coverage. Global maps of the methane total column mixing ratios, noted X_{CH_4} , are drawn from these measurements using a full-physics approach which accounts for geophysical variables besides methane (e.g., albedo, water vapor, aerosol optical depth) that could interfere in the retrieval process. Different X_{CH_4} products, obtained through different retrieval algorithms, have been used in this study and are described in the following subsections. As multiple TROPOMI X_{CH_4} products are used, later sections on comparing with GHGSat data will include comparisons to the different TROPOMI X_{CH_4} products. Having these two TROPOMI X_{CH_4} products provide additional robustness in the interpretation of the TROPOMI methane data and results.

3.2.1.1 Operational TROPOMI XCH₄

We use the (reprocessed for dates preceding July 26th, 2022) operational TROPOMI XCH₄ product version 2.4 [RD-20], which is based on the RemoTeC retrieval algorithm [RD-21, RD-22] and includes an improved albedo correction compared to previous versions [RD-23]. In this study, we analysed the TROPOMI XCH₄ data for the year 2022 including on days that overlap with the GHGSat satellite and aircraft data provided for this study. The comparisons of the plume enhancements were carried out with the scientific SRON TROPOMI product using the same retrieval algorithm as used for the operational TROPOMI XCH₄ data product, allowing more flexibility in analyzing the results.

3.2.1.2 WFMD TROPOMI XCH₄

To provide an additional measures of emission estimate from TROPOMI, we also used column-averaged dry air mole fraction methane (XCH₄) from the L2 TROPOMI/WFMD XCH₄ product (v1.8) derived by the University of Bremen (IUP). The IUP product uses the Weighting Function Modified Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (WFM-DOAS) retrieval algorithm that is based on a linear least-square fitting method by perturbing (scaling or shifting) pre-selected atmospheric vertical profiles. Vertical columns of methane (and carbon monoxide) are simultaneously retrieved from sun-normalised radiance spectra (taken from L1b V01.00.00 calibrated spectra) using a linearised radiative transfer model with methane retrieved from the 2311-2315 nm and 2320 – 2338 nm spectral windows [RD-24, RD-25]. The IUP product is commissioned by the ESA GHG-CCI (Greenhouse Gas Climate Change Initiative), provides an additional TROPOMI CH₄ dataset for comparison to the operational ESA and scientific SRON data products. To assess the methane emissions over Madrid, we analysed the time period from 1st January 2018 up to 31st August 2022 which includes the time period of the GHGSat satellite data period and the GHGSat aircraft campaign. At the time this data analysis was conducted, the V1.8 published data did not overlap with some of the GHGSat aircraft flights in which case the University of Bremen (internal communications with Oliver Schneising) generated preliminary data (V1.8T) corresponding to these months. Since then the V1.8T data products have become part of the official V1.8 L2 TROPOMI/WFMD XCH₄ product.

3.2.2 GHGSat satellite measurements and data

The Canadian company GHGSat operates a constellation of 9 small satellites (GHGSat C1-C8 and demonstrator GHGSat-D) that can provide images of methane concentration enhancement at high spatial resolution (25 x 25 m²) over small target areas of ~10 x 15

km² [RD-26]. The plumes they detect are analyzed using the mass-balance based Integrated Mass Enhancement (IME, see Sect. 4.2.1.1) method [RD-13] with 10-m wind speeds from the GEOS-FP reanalysis product [RD-28]. GHGSat reports a points-source detection limit of ~100 kg/hr [RD-29], and successfully detected a 200 kg/hr point source in a single-blind controlled release experiment [RD-30]. For more diffuse sources like landfills the detection limit is likely somewhat worse but GHGSat has detected emissions down to ~200 kg/hr.

For this study, 10 satellite observations in 2022 have been obtained to GHGSat, at dates matching clear sky coverage for TROPOMI observations. They are summarized in Table 3-1. For each observation, the deliverable includes a set of files providing retrieval results at pixel-level for albedo, methane concentration enhancement, methane uncertainty, and quality flag; detected plume masks and corresponding emission rate results obtained with IME (calibrated for point sources, see Section 3.3.2.1.1); and auxiliary information.

Date	Satellite name	Observation ID	Number of detected plumes
2022-02-28	C2	AY-1E_Z	2
2022-03-01	C2	AYA1E_Z	2
2022-04-03	C2	AYf8j_Z	2
2022-05-06	C2	AZC1E_Z	2
2022-05-31	C2	AZa1yUz	3
2022-06-05	C1	7ZeATUz	2
2022-06-27	C1	7ZyLyUz	2
2022-07-01	C2	A_52TUz	2
2022-07-08	C1	7_B2TUz	3
2022-07-31	C1	7_X8yUz	2

Table 3-1 Summary of the 10 satellite observations obtained from GHGSat.

The methane plumes obtained by GHGSat can be associated to three different facilities: (1) Las Dehesas landfill; (2) Las Dehesas biodigestion plant close to the landfill, hereafter called “Las Dehesas Plant” (only detected on 2022-05-31); and (3) Pinto landfill.

3.2.3 GHGSat aircraft measurements and data

In addition to the 10 satellite observations procured from GHGSat, a complementary aircraft campaign was conducted using GHGSat’s aircraft-adapted instrument, GHGSat-AV. The AIR product provides methane concentration enhancements at 1 x 1 m² resolution over many ~1.5 km² frames in the direction of the flightpath and has a quoted detection limit of 10 kg/hr, allowing for the detection of smaller plumes and improved source attribution. Both landfills were observed over multiple passes, with an 8–15-minute turnaround time between approaches. As there is overlap between these frames, we have to account for emitters being detected multiple times. The procedure to do so is described in Section 3.3.2.2 (with Figure 3-13 illustrating the observation approach).

For this study, airborne measurements were taken across the first two days of July 2022 over both Pinto and Las Dehesas, details of which are summarized in Table 3-2. This results in one coincident GHGSat, GHGAir and TROPOMI observation on 1st July 2022. The airborne data set includes the same products as provided with the SAT product. Unlike the SAT product, GHGSat-AV emissions are quantified using a Cross-Sectional Flux (CSF) approach, detailed in [RD-13], as its simpler physical basis is more appropriate at such high resolution.

Date	Landfill	Number of frames	Number of detected plumes	Number of overpasses
2022-07-01	Pinto	28	57	4
	Las Dehesas	21	16	6
2022-07-02	Pinto	42	37	5
	Las Dehesas	27	34	6

Table 3-2 Summary of the 10 aircraft observations obtained during GHGSat aircraft campaign, July 2022.

3.3 INTERCOMPARISONS

This section describes intercomparisons of both measurements and emission quantifications. Section 3.3.1 describes the comparison of GHGSat enhancements to TROPOMI enhancements using both the operational and WFMD methane products. Section 3.3.2 describes the comparison between the different emission estimates and first introduces the mass balance and inverse modelling approaches used to quantify emissions from both TROPOMI products (3.3.2.1), followed by the processing of the GHGSat aircraft emission plumes to prevent double counting (3.3.2.2). Section 3.3.2.3 presents the different emission estimates: E-PRTR reported emissions, TROPOMI-based estimates, GHGSat satellite estimates, and GHGSat aircraft estimates. Section 3.3.2.4 compares all the different emission estimates. Section 3.3.3 describes a spatial comparison of the satellite data within the facility as well as additional high-resolution satellite analysis to understand the found patterns.

3.3.1 Plume methane enhancements

In this section we present the comparisons between the methane enhancements as determined with the two TROPOMI XCH₄ products (see section 3.2.1) and the GHGSat satellite methane enhancements.

3.3.1.1 Enhancement comparison between GHGSat and the TROPOMI WFMD XCH₄ product

In order to conduct an intercomparison between collocated TROPOMI and GHGSat methane enhancements satellite observations, it was first necessary to resample GHGSat pixel data to the spatial resolution of L2 TROPOMI WFMD XCH₄ pixels. This was done by averaging GHGSat pixels within the bounds of the original TROPOMI pixels (using corner coordinates from each TROPOMI ground point), producing CH₄ enhancements on an identical pixel grid. Only pixels included within the plume mask provided by GHGSat were included in the resampling, all remaining pixels were set to zero. We compared the methane concentration enhancement between co-located TROPOMI pixels (by subtracting

pixel concentration from the background (see Sect 3.3.2.1.1 for details) and resampled GHGSat pixels, shown in *Figure 3-2* and *Figure 3-3* and summarized in *Table 3-3*. For conciseness, only six of the ten comparisons are shown. One day (2022-06-27) contained no quality TROPOMI pixels over the site and was therefore excluded from analysis.

Figure 3-2 Examples of GHGSat measurements resampled to the pixel grid of L2 WFMD TROPOMI XCH4 pixels, with enhancements compared for co-incident pixels, conducted with only GHGSat pixels that are contained within the plume mask provided by GHGSat. These three represent “good” comparisons, where the GHGSat plume is well enhanced above the background and covers multiple TROPOMI pixels.

Figure 3-3 Examples of GHGSat measurements resampled to the pixel grid of TROPOMI, with enhancements compared for co-incident pixels, conducted with only GHGSat pixels that are contained within the plume mask provided by GHGSat. These three represent “poor” comparisons, where the GHGSat enhancement is small, and the plume covers a smaller spatial extent.

On average, we find an average difference between TROPOMI and resampled GHGSat satellite data to be 10.1 ppbv with TROPOMI 18% higher than GHGSat for the selected dates analysed. For low emission days with small plumes (2022-04-03, 2022-05-06 and 2022-06-05), agreement is poor, with the GHGSat enhancement being averaged down to background levels (i.e. close to 0 ppbv). For days with stronger and geometrically larger plumes which cover numerous TROPOMI pixels (2022-02-38, 2022-03-01 and 2022-05-31), the comparison between the two instruments generally improves.

This comparison faced three fundamental issues and these limitations are discussed below.

Firstly, the column density of methane observed over a source, within a pixel of shape $L \times L$, generally increases with decreasing L [RD-26]. Due to GHGSat's 25 m resolution, GHGSat is able to observe much smaller plumes and as a result returns much greater per-pixel values, which allows for enhanced detection of smaller and/or weaker plumes. Equally, observations from TROPOMI ($7 \times 7 \text{ km}^2$ pixels, adapted to $7 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$ since 2019) return lower per-pixel values, and as plumes account for a much smaller fraction of the whole pixel's footprint, the enhancement is averaged down over a much greater area. This makes comparisons between GHGSat and TROPOMI challenging, as the fundamental

viewing geometry influences the detected enhancement. Resampling GHGSat, in many cases, meant that the enhancement was suppressed so greatly, as it was averaged over a much larger area, that the enhancement tended to zero.

Date	Number of pixels	Average Difference TROPOMI - resampled GHGSat [ppbv]	Average Difference TROPOMI - resampled GHGSat [%]
28-02-2022	2	13	76.8
01-03-2022	5	1.92	27.2
03-04-2022	2	23.5	97.6
31-05-2022	4	11.7	97.7
06-05-2022	3	2.89	40.8
05-06-2022	2	3.95	95.5
27-06-2022	0	0	0.0
01-07-2022	3	4.84	82.6
08-07-2022	3	25.3	87.2
31-07-2022	2	4.53	71.5

Table 3-3 Summary of the difference between TROPOMI and GHGSat resampled enhancements.

Secondly, TROPOMI views a much broader region, covering both the landfills, Madrid and the wider area. Emissions from urban activities as well as nearby landfills (which are smaller but will certainly contribute diffuse methane to the environment) will all be accumulated within the larger footprint. GHGSat on the other hand observes over a small 15km² footprint, where almost the entirety of the enhancement, within each pixel in the plume mask, will be from the landfills in question. GHGSat is resampled assuming the enhancement outside of the plume mask is zero, and therefore will not include any regional diffuse CH₄, potentially leading to an underestimation.

Finally, TROPOMI overpasses Madrid around 13:30 local time, whereas the GHGSat observations provided were taken anywhere from 09:00 – 11:00 local time. This temporal separation means we are not observing the same air parcel due to changing meteorology and/or emission rates. Madrid also experiences rapid changes to its wind field, where wind directions can flip 180° and wind speeds can vary dramatically over a single hour, particularly during summer months. This means that regardless of the previous two issues, we are not observing the same plume and therefore cannot expect perfect correlation in the enhancement.

Unfortunately, despite the “good” comparison cases, the fundamental issues described above still remain, and may explain the difference between the larger TROPOMI enhancement values and the much smaller GHGSat resampled enhancements.

3.3.1.2 Enhancement comparison between GHGSat and the operational TROPOMI XCH₄ product

For a reliable intercomparison between TROPOMI and GHGSat data, we have to 1) compare satellite information on the same spatial resolution, and 2) translate TROPOMI total column mixing ratios of CH₄ (XCH₄) to enhancements of CH₄ with respect to a background value, as is measured by GHGSat. For the first point, we conducted a

resampling of GHGSat data to the ground pixel footprints of the corresponding TROPOMI overpass from the same day. In the centre, the size of the ground pixel is about $7 \times 5.5 \text{ km}^2$, but it can be as big as $7 \times 30 \text{ km}^2$ at the edges of an orbit. To account for this, we resampled the GHGSat data to the specific size of ground pixels of the individual TROPOMI orbits.

In order to address the second point, we estimate the background of XCH_4 in the TROPOMI orbit and subtract this from the peak XCH_4 , within the GHGSat field of view (FoV). Integral to this is the estimation of the background. We investigated two different ways of determining this, firstly to take an off-source mean of the XCH_4 value. This approach suffered from limited coverage in the TROPOMI data due to clouds, therefore as a second approach we also calculated the background for XCH_4 with the CAMS atmospheric model, however the results were inconclusive.

To achieve increased coverage in the TROPOMI data, we reprocessed retrievals from the scientific SRON TROPOMI product using the same retrieval algorithm as used for the operational TROPOMI XCH_4 data product, with a relaxed pre-filter for quality assurance. The reprocessed L2 data were then post-filtered with a quality flag of > 0.4 . An example of the improved coverage can be seen in Figure 3-4. The reprocessing of XCH_4 for the 31st July failed, and therefore TROPOMI data for this day were taken from the operational data product, with no post-filtering applied. Accounting for this, we had in total six days of data which had sufficient coverage in TROPOMI data for intercomparison, and we present wide FoV images of these in Figure 3-5.

There is a systematic time difference of around 3 hours between GHGSat and TROPOMI, with TROPOMI overpassing Madrid around 13:30 local time, and GHGSat between 09:00 and 11:00 local time in Figure 3-6. In one of the TROPOMI orbits (31st May), the peak XCH_4 value was detected downwind from the source and lay outside of the GHGSat FoV. It is possible that given the three-hour lag between TROPOMI and GHGSat, by the time TROPOMI detected the plume it had moved position due to changing wind. To account for this, we calculated the maximum TROPOMI XCH_4 concentration for this day from a bounding box which encapsulated the detected plume.

Figure 3-4 Overpasses from 31st May of TROPOMI operational product (left panel) compared to the scientific product with relaxed pre-filter (right panel) illustrating the gain in spatial coverage.

Figure 3-5: TROPOMI overpasses from days where GHGSat measurements took place, for orbits where there are enough data over the collocated source (indicated by the black box). Note that the bottom right plot was created using the operational TROPOMI product, with no quality assurance applied. Also clearly seen is the downwind maximum of XCH₄ on 31st May (middle left panel).

Figure 3-6: Resampled CH₄ plumes detected with GHGSat for days where TROPOMI L2 data are available for intercomparison. Original plumes as measured by GHGSat, and having GHGSat provided plume masks applied, are plotted on the left. On the right are the resampled plumes to the TROPOMI grid for the specific ground pixel size of corresponding TROPOMI overpass. The varying size of ground pixel is evident, highlighting the necessity of resampling the GHGSat measurements onto the ground pixel footprint applicable for the actual TROPOMI overpass that day.

Fig 3-6 continued.

To summarise our findings, we present a correlation plot between GHGSat and TROPOMI CH₄ enhancements in Figure 3-7. We find that there is a high correlation between the two satellites ($R=0.86$), where strong plumes detected by GHGSat correspond to strong plumes seen by TROPOMI and vice versa.

Figure 3-7 Correlation plot between TROPOMI and GHGSat CH₄ enhancements over Madrid. Circles indicate GHGSat measurements taken with the C1 satellite, and crosses correspond to those from C2. The pink point which has the maximum enhancement is the 31st May, where we calculated the maximum CH₄ concentration for TROPOMI from a bounding box offset spatially from the GHGSat FoV.

Despite the good correlation observed between satellites, a significant bias of 21.2 ppb, with TROPOMI measuring the higher enhancement, is seen. This is not surprising given the sensitivities of the two satellites to different spatial resolutions, and there are a number of explanations for the bias. The most fundamental one is that TROPOMI measures more wide scale CH₄ enhancement than GHGSat, either from more diffuse sources, or point sources outside the GHGSat FoV. Furthermore, the plume from the landfills themselves drops under the GHGSat detection limit further downwind from the source as the plume disperses but that downwind enhancement still adds to the total enhancement seen by TROPOMI.

Other sources of bias include different vertical sensitivity in the satellites, as well as the time delay between the satellites which may result in different meteorological conditions at the time of observation. Furthermore, the down-sampled CH₄ enhancements of GHGSat span only a handful of TROPOMI pixels, making intercomparison of the two satellites challenging. Stronger and longer emission plumes would result in a more reliable intercomparison and may help reduce this bias. Finally, in order to directly compare the two satellites, we have to convert XCH₄ concentrations as measured by TROPOMI into CH₄ enhancements, as measured by GHGSat. This requires good knowledge of the background XCH₄ which is subtracted from the peak XCH₄ value.

3.3.2 Emissions

This subsection describes the comparison between the different emission estimates. Section 3.3.2.1 describes the TROPOMI quantifications, Section 3.3.2.2 describes how the GHGSat aircraft plumes are processed to prevent double counting, Section 3.3.2.3 describes all the emission estimates including reported emissions, and Section 3.3.2.4 compares all the different emission estimates.

3.3.2.1 TROPOMI emission quantification methodology

This section describes the mass balance approaches used with both the operational and WFMD TROPOMI methane products as well as the inversion-based approach used together with the operational data.

3.3.2.1.1 Mass balance

Mass balance using the operational TROPOMI XCH4 product

For the mass-balance approach we follow the Integrated Mass Enhancement (IME) approach as outlined for TROPOMI in [RD-18]. The IME method was first proposed by [RD-31] and its calibration and operational use improved by [RD-13]. IME approaches first require masking methane plumes in TROPOMI XCH4 data. We do so by applying a dilation algorithm starting from the known source location to select enhanced pixels and compute the azimuth direction of the plume's elongated axis. The methane background value $X_{CH_4,bg}$ and its standard deviation $\sigma_{\Delta X_{CH_4}}$ are then evaluated from a sample of TROPOMI observations taken upwind of the source. The pixels that verify $X_{CH_4} \geq X_{CH_4,bg} + 1.5\sigma_{\Delta X_{CH_4}}$ and which are contained within a $0.7^\circ \times 1.0^\circ$ box aligned with the plume direction are included in the plume mask.

To quantify the emission rate associated with a masked plume, the IME method effectively relates the emission rate Q of the source to the plume's total methane mass and residence time in the atmosphere, which gives:

$$Q = \frac{U_{eff}}{L} \sum_i \Delta X_{CH_4,i} a_i \quad (1)$$

with U_{eff} , the effective wind speed transporting the plume, $L = \sqrt{\sum_i a_i}$ the plume length, $\Delta X_{CH_4,i}$ the total column methane enhancement of the i -th plume mask pixel, and a_i the area of this pixel.

Plume transport includes complicated three-dimensional transport and turbulent effects that require computer-intensive simulations to be precisely accounted for. Through IME, the overall impact of those effects is included into a single effective wind speed U_{eff} value. It is calibrated against the 10-m wind speed provided by meteorological models over a set of Large Eddy Simulations (LES) made for known synthetic emission rates, and re-sampled according to a given instrument's characteristics (spatial resolution, noise model, etc.). Here, we use the effective wind speed calibration coefficients given for TROPOMI in [RD-18].

For a given plume, we use the ensemble approach that perturbs all the different IME inputs described in [RD-18] to evaluate the emission rate uncertainty. The varied inputs include the masking threshold, background concentration, using three different wind products, applying 50% perturbation to those wind speeds, and a 5% perturbation to the effective wind speed coefficient. Finally, we report the ensemble average and ensemble standard deviation as the inferred emission rate and a conservative estimate for the associated uncertainty, respectively.

Mass balance using the WFMD TROPOMI XCH4 product

To quantify emissions from the IUP WFMD TROPOMI XCH4 product, we similarly used the IME approach of [RD-13] using more specifically the method implemented by [RD-27].

The IME method is based on the relationship between the source rate (Q) in kg/s and the mass of the whole plume (IME) in kg downwind of that source. To relate the source rate to the plume mass, the residence time (τ) of CH_4 in the plume is defined as the wind speed (U) in m/s over the plume length (L) in m as follows [RD-13].

$$Q = \frac{1}{\tau} IME = \frac{U}{L} IME \quad (2)$$

The approach implemented by [RD-27] relies on a persistent anomaly detection to first extract the methane enhancements (over the background signal) associated with the Madrid urban domain (Figure 3-8). These enhancements are then used to identify an appropriate area of interest (AOI) to estimate emission source rates within each S5p TROPOMI overpass. Within the chosen domain, L2 variables from each WFMD TROPOMI L2 XCH4 orbit were first oversampled to a regular grid with a 0.01 degrees resolution (to

generate L3U data) and then used to identify “hotspots” to generate a map of persistent anomalies. These anomalies are calculated per day on a pixel-to-pixel basis by assessing if the methane concentration within a selected pixel is higher or equal to the median XCH₄ + 2σ within the domain. To ensure the high XCH₄ concentrations are not outliers in the number of anomalous pixels and data coverage registered for each day, we applied the condition that the expected percentage of outliers in a 2σ distribution is 5% and therefore established a 2.5% threshold for the tail of the distribution as our expected high value outliers. Using this information, the days with more than 2.5% anomalies were discarded and a bitmask (1/0) generated by normalising the sum of anomalies in each pixel location with the number of days analysed to create a hotspot map. Figure 3-9 presents a hotspot map of persistent anomalies generated for the Madrid landfill sites using WFMD TROPOMI XCH₄ data from 2018-01-01 to 2022-08-31 (timeseries shown in Figure 3-10). The largest density of XCH₄ anomalies (i.e. elevated methane concentrations) are located directly over the location of the Pinto and Las Dehasas landfill sites (indicated by the green/yellow pixel colours). Using this information, we identified a persistent methane signal around the landfill sites that informed the extent for the AOI considered for the calculation of fluxes with the IME method.

Figure 3-8 Left: Madrid domain (pink), area of interest (AOI) (purple) and landfill site locations (points); Right: Zoom into Madrid landfill sites.

Figure 3-9 Hotspot map showing the normalised number of days with XCH₄ anomalies for the Bremen L3u data within the AOI of the Madrid landfill sites, with the location of the study sites.

Figure 3-10 Time series of the mean (μ) \pm standard deviation (σ) over the Madrid landfill sites AOI for all available L3u WFMD TROPOMI XCH₄ data. The shaded grey area highlighted as Bremen data v1.8T is now part of the official V1.8 product. Top: XCH₄ concentrations in ppbv; Bottom: Local wind speed extracted from ERA 5 land reanalysis at the closest overpass hour.

Using the AOI defined by the persistent anomaly detection, each WFMD TROPOMI XCH₄ orbit was then analysed to identify the individual enhancement and background concentration for each day before emission rates are calculated. To solve for the IME in Eq. 2 we created a plume mask that defined the plume area in WFMD TROPOMI XCH₄ data used for each day. We first created a preliminary mask that relies on a threshold method [RD-32] which uses automatic imaging threshold processing in which pixel intensity (or XCH₄ concentration in this case) are separated into two classes (corresponding to foreground and background values). To establish the background, we output an upper threshold value and all pixels with a concentration higher than this threshold value are assumed to be foreground cluster and all pixels outside of this cluster are assigned as background concentrations. For each day, methane enhancement maps are generated by subtracting the mean background XCH₄ from the XCH₄ concentration for each spatial pixel within the AOI (Figure 3-11 left and middle panels). This preliminary mask, or threshold mask, was then refined with a Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) method [RD-33] to separate the plumes into distinct clusters and keep the cluster corresponding to the plume originating from the source (see Figure 3-11 right panels). These maps, along with 10 metre wind vector information extracted from ERA 5 Land reanalysis data (0.1° x 0.1° spatial and 1-hourly temporal resolution, RD-34), act as our reference when selecting the days with significant downwind enhancements originating from the source region. For the Madrid landfill sites, the DBSCAN method was applied to coordinates at the midpoint between Landfill 1 and Landfill 2 to maintain the plume cluster closest to the sites. A successful mask is considered one located within 10 km of the sites and without disconnected pixels or gaps within the plume mask. Once a representative plume mask is calculated, the plume mask and methane concentration enhancement for each day is visually inspected following which Eq 2. is applied to calculate the emission source rate. Our initial application of IME was performed using a strict selection criterion (i.e. the minimum coverage over AOI was set to 60% with a minimum enhancement threshold), however this resulted in a low number of selected plumes over the 2018 to 2022 time period analysed. We repeated application of the IME with a relaxed selection (combined with visual inspection) which better captured the smaller plume features and methane enhancements that were omitted by stricter selection criteria.

Figure 3-11 Methane enhancement and plume masks for Madrid landfill sites on 11th November 2021 and 27th May 2022. Left: WFMD TROPOMI CH₄ enhancement map with wind vectors; Middle: corresponding plume mask using the thresholding; Right: corresponding plume mask for the IME method using thresholding and DBSCAN.

There are limitations when applying the IME method to the TROPOMI data in this study such as assigning plume pixels, the proximity of the sources that cause overlaps in the emissions, and the wind speed information. Given that the inputs for the IME method are plume length, CH₄ enhancement values and wind speed, these will all contribute to the emission quantification error. We quantify an error for the emission source rate for each detected plume by taking the quadrature of selected sources of uncertainty which include: 1) the standard deviation of the local wind speed (u_{ws}) and the average local wind speed (ws), 2) the standard deviation of the background XCH₄ (u_B) and the average background XCH₄ (B), 3) the standard deviation of the plume enhancement CH₄ (u_{enh}) and the average plume enhancement CH₄ (enh), 4) the standard deviation of the XCH₄ uncertainty ($u_{XCH_4,unc}$) from the IUP WFMD TROPOMI XCH₄ data.

As wind speed and direction are the largest source of error in emission quantification, Varon *et al.*, 2019 [RD-51] suggests using large eddy simulations to arrive at a relationship between the 10-metre wind speed and an effective wind speed. Due to the time available for this study, we used an effective wind speed equal to the 10-metre wind speed similar to the approach in [RD-35] (where enhancements of ~30 ppb comparable to this study were obtained). However, we take into account this limitation by calculating a range in emission source rate using a ± 1 m/s wind speed perturbation to define the change in emission rate if the wind speed was biased by ± 1 m/s. Whilst we use ERA 5 Land wind fields due to its higher spatial resolution (with the expectation that it can account for surface interactions more effectively), we performed some inter-comparisons with 10-metre wind fields from ERA 5 single level (0.25° x 0.25° hourly) wind data [RD-36] for the Madrid region. Analysis of 13.00 UTC and 10.00 UTC wind fields from both ERA 5 land and ERA 5 single level show differences in wind speed and wind direction (See appendix Figure 5-1). Further comparisons to NCEP/GFS wind fields (not shown) shows that the wind fields over Madrid region not only switch direction but can change from 13km/hr to 3km/hr in a matter of hours.

Investigation of suitable wind field treatment will be conducted in the future and more immediately, future iterations of our IME algorithm will incorporate wind calibration with large eddy simulations for effective wind calculation.

3.3.2.1.2 Atmospheric inversion using the operational TROPOMI XCH₄ product

A mass balance approach estimates a single emission rate for the plume observed in satellite data. While this is perfectly acceptable for plumes observed at facility scale with high-resolution instruments, it does not give a full characterization of underlying emissions at TROPOMI scale. Many different sectors and facilities may contribute to the underlying emissions that contribute to a plume (or any other methane concentration field) observed in TROPOMI. In addition, mass balance approaches use one effective wind, while the wind field is 3 dimensional in space and varies over time. This is better captured using an atmospheric transport model.

Atmospheric inversion

Atmospheric inversion [RD-37] can help to take better advantage of TROPOMI data, and to potentially separate the contributions of different sectors or facilities. This approach leverages forward atmospheric transport modelling combined with an inversion approach to obtain the fluxes that best fit a set of methane observations (TROPOMI in this case). Among the numerous different inverse strategies that exist, we apply here the analytical solution to the inference problem defined in the framework of Optimal Estimation [RD-38]. The relationship between observations and emissions is defined by the following equation:

$$\mathbf{y} = F(\mathbf{x}) + \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{y} is the measurement vector that contains methane observations, \mathbf{x} is the state vector that contains surface fluxes, F represents the forward model, which is the atmospheric transport model in this case, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ represents the observational error including modelling errors. Considering algebraically convenient Gaussian statistics and a linear forward model represented by the Jacobian matrix \mathbf{K} , the analytical solution to the inverse problem is vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, that minimizes the Bayesian cost function χ^2 . They are given by:

$$\chi^2 = (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_a)^T \mathbf{S}_a^{-1} (\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_a) + \gamma (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{x})^T \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{x}) \quad (4)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{x}_a + (\mathbf{S}_a^{-1} + \gamma \mathbf{K}^T \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} \mathbf{K})^{-1} \mathbf{K}^T \gamma \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} (\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{K}\mathbf{x}_a) \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{x}_a is the a priori state vector that describes the knowledge of surface fluxes before using the information brought by methane observations, \mathbf{S}_a is the prior error covariance matrix, \mathbf{S}_e is the observational error covariance matrix, and γ is a regularization parameter that adjusts the weight of the information brought by observations in the inverse problem to prevent overfitting. The optimal solution of the inverse problem $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ is both constrained by the prior (it does not deviate too much from it), while also matching the methane observations as best as possible. Furthermore, we also have $\hat{\mathbf{S}}$, the a posteriori error covariance matrix of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$:

$$\hat{\mathbf{S}} = (\mathbf{S}_a^{-1} + \gamma \mathbf{K}^T \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} \mathbf{K})^{-1} \mathbf{K}^T \gamma \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} \quad (6)$$

and \mathbf{A} , the averaging kernel matrix that gives the sensitivity of the optimized solution to the true – but unknown – fluxes:

$$\mathbf{A} = (\mathbf{S}_a^{-1} + \gamma \mathbf{K}^T \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} \mathbf{K})^{-1} \mathbf{K}^T \gamma \mathbf{S}_e^{-1} \mathbf{K} \quad (7)$$

The diagonal elements of \mathbf{A} are comprised between 0 and 1, and help evaluate, for each state vector element, whether the observations or the a priori state most influence the posterior result. The closer they are to 1, the higher the influence of the observations on the posterior result.

Forward modeling using the WRF model

Here, we perform a Weather Research & Forecasting (WRF) model (version 4.1, RD-39) simulation for 2022. We simulate a 612 x 612 km² domain at 18 km resolution centred on Madrid, with two nested domains of 6 km and 2 km resolutions (and covering 384 x 330 km² and 92 x 92 km² respectively), centred on Madrid, while also avoiding their boundaries crossing the strong elevation slopes around the Madrid area. Figure 3-12 **WRF simulation setup with three domains at increasingly fine resolution towards the Madrid urban area and neighboring landfills**. illustrates this simulation setup.

Figure 3-12 WRF simulation setup with three domains at increasingly fine resolution towards the Madrid urban area and neighboring landfills.

The simulation uses meteorological fields from the National Centre for Environmental Prediction (NCEP, RD-49) and initial and 6-hourly methane background boundary conditions at 0.25° x 0.25° from the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS) [RD-40]. WRF has been set to use the CONUS physics options as transport configuration and to provide hourly output.

The simulation has been performed using 19 different tracers that include domain-wide and sector-wise emission maps from EDGAR v6 [RD-41] and [RD-42], as well as point sources located at Las Dehasas (40.3225°N, -3.5919°E), Pinto (40.2640 °N, -3.6322°E), Toledo (39.8591°N, -4.1641°E), Valladolid (41.6899°N, -4.6451°E) and Leon (42.5 °N, -5.5°E). Methane concentration fields simulated separately for these different tracers, and sampled at the timestamps closest to TROPOMI overpasses, enable to build the Jacobian Matrix K that was introduced above.

3.3.2.2 GHGSat aircraft emission calculation

The flight plan executed during the airborne campaign made sure that all succeeding frames are partially overlapping, as well as different flight lines, so that no observation gaps remain over the surveyed area. The GHGSat analysis of their airborne data is performed for each frame separately, thus yielding plume source locations and emission rates specific to each frame. Figure 3-13 schematically illustrates this observation and processing strategy: individual frames are represented by oval shapes and two flight lines are depicted: a first one with red and yellow frames, and a second one with blue and green frames. Crosses denote source locations as analysed by GHGSat for each frame separately.

Because of the overlaps between frames and flight lines, some sources identified by GHGSat may be observed several times for the same facility and campaign day. Thus, to

correct for double-counts, we globally analyse GHGSat frame-wise plume sources and emission rates for each facility and campaign day. We define as “identical”, the plume sources from different frames or flight lines that are within 0.0005° of one another. Their respective coordinates are averaged, and their emission rates and related uncertainties are averaged together as independent Gaussian variables. **Table 3-4** compares for each facility and campaign day, the number of plume sources obtained for all frames separately with the number of sources obtained after accounting for the double-counts in the overlapping frames and flight lines.

Figure 3-13 Schematic representation of GHGSat airborne data structure, observation strategy and potential double counts that have to be accounted for. The cyan and magenta circles depict individual plume sources that are considered as identical.

Facility	Date	Number of plume sources	Number of sources after double count correction
Las Dehesas	2022-07-01	19	14
Las Dehesas Plant	2022-07-01	1	1
Pinto	2022-07-01	58	48
Las Dehesas	2022-07-02	34	25
Las Dehesas Plant	2022-07-02	0	0
Pinto	2022-07-02	38	31
TOTAL	-	150	119

Table 3-4 Plume sources obtained from GHGSat airborne data before and after accounting for double-counts due to overlapping frames and flight lines.

3.3.2.3 Emission estimates

This section describes all the available/obtained emission data from reporting (3.3.2.3.1), TROPOMI (3.3.2.3.2), GHGSat satellites (3.3.2.3.3), and GHGSat aircraft (3.3.2.3.4).

3.3.2.3.1 Reported emissions

The European Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (E-PRTR, RD-43), established by the European Commission, supported by the European Environment Agency, and linked to the EU industrial emissions directive sets out the reporting requirements for over 50 000 industrial facilities across Europe and EU member states (EEA,2022). See <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02006R0166-20200101> for details.

For active landfill sites, the requirements state that air emissions, including those of methane are reported annually in units of kg/year and emissions can be calculated, measured or estimated. For the two landfill sites of interest in Madrid, we extracted annual methane emissions reported by the Pinto and Las Dehesas facilities from 2007 to 2021 (2022 annual emissions, corresponding to this study are not yet available). As a first check, the E-PRTR reported emissions for both facilities can act as a reference for comparison to the GHGSat satellite and aircraft calculated emissions in 2022. Therefore, we extracted the E-PRTR facility level emission data for Pinto and Las Dehesas shown in Figure 3-14 *Annual methane emissions [2007 to 2021] reported by the Pinto and Las Dehesas facilities to the E-PRTR register.* for comparison to methane emissions calculated in this study. Based on engagement with the Las Dehesas facility operators the reported methane emissions are estimated from the gas captured by the biogas processing plant with an assumed percentage of methane lost (uncaptured). For Pinto, the source of reported methane emissions is unknown. For Las Dehesas the reported emissions vary between 5000 t/yr and 9000 t/yr between 2007 and 2019 (highest in 2013 at 1100 kg/hr), however the emissions show a significant reduction in the years 2020 and 2021 where reported emissions fall to 2500 t/yr which is equivalent to an emission rate of 285 kg/hr.

Figure 3-14 Annual methane emissions [2007 to 2021] reported by the Pinto and Las Dehesas facilities to the E-PRTR register.

3.3.2.3.2 TROPOMI emissions

This section describes the results of the mass balance approaches applied to the WFMD and operational TROPOMI methane products as well as the insights from the inversion-based approach applied to the operational product.

3.3.2.3.2.1 Emissions quantified using the WFDM TROPOMI XCH4 product

Mass-balance approach

Using the approach highlighted in Sect 3.3.2.1.1, the methane emissions over the Madrid landfill AOI are presented in Figure 3-15 for TROPOMI overpasses between January 2018 and August 2022. In total 199 plumes were selected for analysis (using the selection criteria and visual inspection described in Sect 3.3.2.1.1). **Table 3-5** presents the number of plumes detected for each year with the mean and standard deviation of the emission. Additional information on the mean plume size as well as the range in emission rate given a $\pm 1\text{m/s}$ perturbation in wind speed are also provided.

Figure 3-15 Methane emission estimates [t/hr] for Madrid landfills using the IME method with plumes identified in IUP WFMD TROPOMI XCH4 data from 2018-01-01 to 2022-08-31.

TROPOMI (IUP WFMD)		Emission [t/yr]		Plume Area [km ²]		Emission Range (with $\pm 1\text{m/s}$ perturbation) [t/hr]
Year	Number of Plumes	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean Range
2018	30	12.61	7.88	430.8	334.7	827 – 16.95
2019	36	13.79	8.78	475.3	337.0	9.09 – 18.49
2020	35	16.38	10.98	464.5	300.8	11.28 – 21.48
2021	45	14.50	7.80	378.3	287.1	10.28 – 18.71
2022 (Jan to Aug)	53	14.48	8.50	394.3	300.3	10.89 – 18.07

Table 3-5 Mean methane emission source rates, mean plume size and emission range (given a $\pm 1\text{m/s}$ perturbation in wind speed) for 2018 to 2022 over the Madrid AOI (centred over the Pinto and Las Dehesas landfill sites). Note, 2022 results are for January to August only.

The entire 2018 to 2022 period analysed yields a mean methane emission rate of 14.41 ± 8.76 t/hr and given the 7×5.5 km² size of TROPOMI pixels (7×7 km² in 2018/early 2019), these emissions most likely represent contributions from other emission source contributors, diffuse emissions as well as the hotspot regions captured within the AOI.

To disentangle the contribution the landfills and other emitting sources make to the emissions calculated within the Madrid urban region, the atmospheric inversions using WRF presented in the next section provide more insight into the overall Madrid city emissions with respect to the landfill sector.

3.3.2.3.2.2 Emissions quantified using the operational TROPOMI XCH4 product

Mass-balance approach

All the TROPOMI overpasses of Madrid for the year 2022 have been processed following the method detailed in Sect. 3.3.2.1.1. However, the variability in cloudiness, plume shape and plume enhancement values may sometimes be challenging for a plume masking approach that uses fixed parameters. Hence, a visual inspection of the automatic plume masking and upwind sampling was subsequently performed, yielding a total of 45 overpasses for which the IME results are used. The orbit numbers of those 45 overpasses are listed in the Appendix.

Figure 3-16 shows the timeseries of TROPOMI IME results for 2022. The average emission rate is 14.25 t/hr, with a standard deviation across the selected 45 overpasses of 8.74 t/hr.

Figure 3-16 TROPOMI IME emission rate results for the 45 overpasses that pass visual inspection in 2022.

Atmospheric inversion using WRF

As a first step in applying more sophisticated approaches to estimate emissions, we use a very simple inverse setup that allows us to evaluate the TROPOMI IME emission estimates.

We define a simple state vector composed of three elements: (1) scaling factor for the CAMS-based background; (2) scaling factor for the Las Dehesas methane emission rate; and (3) scaling factor for the Pinto methane emission rate. The a priori value for all scaling factors is 1, and we use GHGSat reported average emission rates for Las Dehesas (2.0 t/hr) and Pinto (2.5 t/hr) to run WRF. In reality, there are other emissions spread throughout the urban area, these are not included in these simulations but should be included in a full evaluation of emissions from the area. The a priori uncertainty is 10% for the scaling of CAMS background and 50% for landfill emission rates.

We include in the measurement vector all the TROPOMI pixels located within the two innermost WRF domains defined in Figure 3-12, for a given overpass. We use the standard deviation of the observed – a priori simulated X_{CH_4} difference to fill the diagonal elements of the observational error covariance matrix. The emission rate obtained with this measurement vector is only valid for the overpass from which observations were used.

For each overpass (listed in the Appendix), two different inversions are performed. The first one uses a standard regularization parameter value $\gamma = 1$ and the second one uses $\gamma = 100000$. The latter overly favours the observations against the prior state in the inverse solution, effectively giving the solution purely based on the observations. Thus, the comparison of these two inversion configurations, which is presented in Table 3-6 (averages over the 45 selected overpasses), enables to evaluate the contribution of the a priori state to the inversion result.

	$\gamma = 1$	$\gamma = 100000$
Annual average of the total landfill emission rate [t/hr]	6.35 ± 2.50 t/hr (N=45)	9.88 ± 6.78 t/hr
Annual average of Las Dehesas landfill averaging kernel sensitivity	0.27	1
Annual average of Pinto landfill averaging kernel sensitivity	0.36	1
Annual average of the correlation coefficient between Las Dehesas and Pinto emission rates	-0.17 (min, max: -0.41, -0.01)	-0.54 (min, max: -0.87, -0.13)

Table 3-6 Inversion results averaged over the 45 selected overpasses, comparing two regularization parameter values.

The total emission rate result obtained with $\gamma = 1$ amounts to 6.35 t/hr, which falls within the large $\pm 1\sigma$ uncertainty range of the IME based estimate. The results of both individual facilities are mostly influenced by the prior, as the averaging kernel sensitivities for separate landfill emission scaling factors are both below 0.5. However, their sum is above 0.5, signifying that a total emission rate for both landfills can be constrained with a contribution of information brought by observations larger than the one coming from the prior. Using \hat{S} off-diagonal coefficients, we find a negative error correlation coefficient between the emission rates of both facilities. Statistical errors overestimating emissions from one landfill would be somewhat compensated with errors underestimating the emissions of the other landfill, and vice versa. This shows that TROPOMI observations do not enable us to constrain emissions from Las Dehesas and Pinto separately.

The result obtained with the exaggerated $\gamma = 100000$ forces Optimal Estimation to overly rely on the observation information, leading to by-construction exaggerated degrees of freedom for both landfill emission scaling factors. We can notice that the total landfill emission rate of 9.88 t/hr is now closer to the average of IME-based estimates. This can be explained by the fact that IME solely relies on information brought by observations, as Optimal Estimation with $\gamma = 100000$. Transport errors leading to spatial discrepancies between simulated and observed plumes result in systematically underestimated WRF-based emission rates. When selecting individual orbits where simulated and observed methane plumes are in fair agreement, such as for orbits 23936 and 25142 showcased in Table 3-7, and in Figure 3-17 and Figure 3-18, respectively, more consistent results with IME are found as expected. These Figures show TROPOMI observations alongside a priori and a posteriori simulated methane fields, and their differences. In these Figures, we notice that simulated – observed errors decrease a posteriori in the vicinity of Madrid urban area, located in the innermost simulation domain depicted by the black rectangle.

	WRF inversion with $\gamma = 100000$	IME
Orbit	23936	
Figure	<i>Figure 3-17</i>	-
Total landfill emission rate [t/hr]	21.37 t/hr	18.20 \pm 10.97 t/hr
Las Dehesas landfill averaging kernel sensitivity	1	-
Pinto landfill averaging kernel sensitivity	1	-
Correlation coefficient between Las Dehesas and Pinto emission rates	-0.73	-
Orbit	25142	
Figure	<i>Figure 3-18</i>	-

Total landfill emission rate [t/hr]	10.62 t/hr	11.07 ± 4.10 t/hr
Las Dehesas landfill averaging kernel sensitivity	1.	-
Pinto landfill averaging kernel sensitivity	1.	-
Correlation coefficient between Las Dehesas and Pinto emission rates	-0.51	-

Table 3-7 Inversion results for two selected orbits, comparing two regularization parameters.

Figure 3-17 Methane total column observed by TROPOMI (top left), simulated for a priori and a posteriori inversion state vectors using WRF (top center and right, resp.), and the corresponding observed – simulated difference (bottom center and right, resp.) for orbit 23936 and $\gamma = 100000$. The black rectangle corresponds to the d03 boundaries shown in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-18 Methane total column observed by TROPOMI (top left), simulated for a priori and a posteriori inversion state vectors using WRF (top center and right, resp.), and the corresponding observed – simulated difference (bottom center and right, resp.) for orbit 25142 and $\gamma = 1$. The black rectangle corresponds to the d03 boundaries shown in Figure 3-12.

Different tests have been performed to explore different state vector configurations, and especially some including domain-wide sector-wise bottom-up emission maps (not shown). Using these maps and optimizing them using single scaling factors implicitly assumes that the distribution of emissions across the map is well-known. However, a comparison of EDGAR [RD-41] and CAMS [RD-44] bottom-up methane emission maps in **Figure 3-19** shows many discrepancies. Hence, WRF runs with tracers simulating methane fields for separate grid elements rather than for domain-wide sector-wise emission maps are necessary to optimally estimate emissions from the urban area of Madrid. Because transport errors are also detrimental to inversion results, future work will also need to account for these errors by considering spatial aggregation of TROPOMI data, and/or different wind products to nudge WRF (e.g., using ERA5 meteorology instead of NCEP).

Figure 3-19 Total methane emission maps prescribed by EDGAR (top) and CAM5 (bottom) bottom-up inventories, at their native resolutions. Red rectangles depict WRF simulation domains shown in Figure 3-2. Madrid city location is shown with the magenta star, and Las Dehesas and Pinto landfills with the blue crosses.

3.3.2.3.3 GHGSat satellite emissions

Plumes detected in the GHGSat observations were originally quantified using the IME method with an effective wind speed calibration corresponding to a point source. However, methane emission sources in landfills are more diffuse pure point sources such as gas

leaks, and [RD-19] showed how this impacts the effective wind speed calibration. For point sources they find: $U_{eff} = 0.34 U_{10m} + 0.42$, with U_{10m} the 10-m wind speed, whereas for area sources $U_{eff} = 0.34 U_{10m} + 0.66$ should be used.

Figure 3-20 shows emission rate time series based on GHGSat satellite observations for both Las Dehasas (excluding the nearby plant, observed just once on May 31st with an emission rate of 1.35 ± 0.77 t/hr) and Pinto landfills, using both the point source (GHGSat default calibration, in light blue) and area source (in dark blue) effective wind calibrations. Las Dehasas and Pinto show an average emission rate of 2.45 ± 1.15 t/hr and 3.20 ± 1.66 t/hr, respectively.

Figure 3-20 Methane emission time series observed by GHGSat satellites for Las Dehasas (top) and Pinto (bottom) landfills, using both the point source (light blue) and area source (dark blue) effective wind calibrations.

These results show a strong correlation between the emission time series of both facilities with a Pearson correlation coefficient of 0.83. Different hypotheses have been considered to explain this strong correlation: (1) similar operational constraints or waste influx apply to both facilities; (2) both landfills are under the influence of similar meteorological drivers such as surface pressure changes [RD-45]; (3) plumes for both facilities are contained within the same GHGSat observation and are processed with similar methods. While the first hypothesis would need to be discussed with on-site operators, we have been able to explore the second and third ones. Regarding meteorology, no significant correlation between meteorological variables (2 m and surface temperature, 2 m humidity, surface pressure, surface pressure change, wind speed, wind direction and precipitation) and emission time series have been observed using GEOS-CF, ERA5 and airport meteorological data (not shown). Regarding the processing of GHGSat observations, sanity checks and independent masking and quantifications have been performed, so far

not explaining the correlation (not shown). In conclusion, explaining this striking correlation between the two facility emission time series remains an open question.

3.3.2.3.4 GHGSat aircraft emissions

Table 3-8 summarizes the total emissions observed per landfill facility and per airborne campaign day, after the double count correction described in Sect. 3.3.2.2. Separate individual sources identified per day and per facility have been treated as independent Gaussian variable, hence the total sum uncertainty was obtained by summing the individual sources in quadrature. As the wind speed used to quantify these emissions is the same across the different plumes, the errors are actually correlated. The most appropriate uncertainty estimate would therefore be between the errors reported in Table 3-8 and the mean of relative uncertainties on the individual plumes (~60%).

Facility	Date	Number of plume sources	Number of sources after double count correction	Total emissions [t/hr]	Total daily emissions [t/hr]
Las Dehesas	2022-07-01	19	14	1.6 ± 0.4	4.0 ± 0.5
Las Dehesas Plant	2022-07-01	1	1	0.015±0.009	
Pinto	2022-07-01	58	48	2.4 ± 0.3	
Las Dehesas	2022-07-02	34	25	4.3 ± 0.7	10.5 ± 1.0
Pinto	2022-07-02	38	31	6.2 ± 0.8	
TOTAL	-	150	119	-	-

Table 3-8 Emissions rates obtained from GHGSat airborne observations, after accounting for double counts.

Total emissions more than double between the first and second day of the airborne campaign. This result may have an operational explanation, that would need to be discussed with operators, but it is important to mention that the wind speed used to quantify emissions is about 0.8-0.9 m/s for July 1st, and about 2.7 m/s for July 2nd. Low wind speed conditions are more challenging to derive accurate emission estimates, we can therefore not exclude an impact of some wind-speed dependent biases in the data analysis pipeline. Unfortunately, no conclusion on this aspect can easily be reached with just two days of flights.

3.3.2.4 Emission intercomparisons

Figure 3-21 compares all GHGSat satellite and airborne observations obtained for this study. The only overlapping day is July 1st, where we find consistent airborne and satellite-

based results for both landfills. Airborne results obtained for July 2nd show higher emission rates that remain within the spread of satellite-based estimates for the entire time period.

Figure 3-22 compares all methane emission rates obtained at different scales for Madrid urban area in 2022. When GHGSat satellite-based emission rates are added for both landfill facilities (including the Las Dehesas plant), we obtain a total emission of 5.78 ± 2.76 t/hr, which is lower than the 14.25 ± 8.74 t/hr and 14.48 ± 8.42 emission estimates obtained using the IME method on the TROPOMI operational and WFDM products, respectively. The two TROPOMI-based estimates are very close to each other, despite them using different retrieval products and different approaches in calculating the IME, for example employing different plume masking methods. TROPOMI being sensitive to methane emissions of the whole Madrid urban area, the difference with the GHGSat estimates suggests that other sectors and facilities than the two landfills observed with GHGSat instruments contribute to the overall total Madrid urban area emissions. Besides, TROPOMI based estimates fairly agree with total bottom-up emissions from EDGAR and CAMS inventory (summed over d03, see Figure 3-11) which amount to 13.24 t/hr and 7.54 t/hr, respectively. The sub-total for solid waste amounts to 3.95 t/hr in EDGAR (30%) and to 5.82 t/hr in CAMS (77%), which falls within the uncertainty range of the GHGSat satellite-based estimate for just the two landfills. Our estimates are slightly higher than, though consistent with the results by [RD-46], who used TROPOMI and TROPOMI+IASI in a wind-assigned anomaly method to find 2017-2020 Madrid area emissions of 7.1 ± 0.6 t/hr and 6.8 ± 1.0 t/hr, respectively. Our average estimates may be higher because the IME methods were only applied to days with plumes in TROPOMI.

The E-PRTR reported values for 2021 for Las Dehesas (0.3 t/hr) and Pinto (1.6 t/hr) add up to 1.9 t/hr. Both the GHGSat satellite and airborne data from 2022 suggest significantly higher emissions for both landfills. Using the landfill-specific calibration, emissions from Las Dehesas are ~8 times larger than reported and emissions from Pinto are ~2 times higher than reported. Using the point-source wind calibration for the GHGSat quantification only reduces estimates by ~20% and hence does not explain the difference. Based on conversations with the landfill operator, the reported emissions are strongly dependent on the assumed capture efficiency of the biogas extraction infrastructure present at the landfill. The GHGSat results suggest that capture efficiency may be overestimated, something that has also been reported for US landfills [RD-47]. As described above, TROPOMI cannot be used to provide estimates for the individual Madrid landfills as they are very close together but shows emissions from the Madrid area as a whole that are larger than the sum of both the E-PRTR-reported and GHGSat-estimated emissions.

Figure 3-21 Comparison of GHGSat satellite and airborne emission rates obtained for this study. The shown satellite data use the area-source effective wind speed calibration (see Figure 3-8). The horizontal lines depict the average emission rates.

Figure 3-22 Comparison of all emission rate estimates obtained for the Madrid urban area and Las Dehesas and Pinto landfills in 2022.

Figure 5-2(see appendix) shows emission estimates calculated using IUP WFMD TROPOMI XCH4 for 2022 with GHGSat satellite and aircraft emissions. For comparison to GHGSat emissions, the reported E-PRTR (total) emissions from the Pinto and Las Dehesas in 2021 are also included. In terms of the mean emissions and standard deviation calculated using the two TROPOMI datasets analysed, there are differences in the data coverage over Madrid and the IME approach uses different meteorological datasets, however despite these differences, the emission estimates are consistent.

3.3.3 Spatial information at facility scale

GHGSat airborne observations have a spatial resolution fine enough to identify a lot of different individual sources with a significant spread in emission rates within each facility. Figure 3-23 and Figure 3-24 show both the spatial distribution of these sources, as well as their respective emission rates (circle size and color) for the 1st (top) and 2nd of July (bottom).

Figure 3-23 Spatial distribution and emission rates of sources observed by GHGSat airborne instrument on July 1st (top) and July 2nd (bottom) in Las Dehesas landfill. The background shows the surface albedo observed during the campaign, and circle size and color both depict the emission rate.

Figure 3-24 Spatial distribution and emission rates of sources observed by GHGSat airborne instrument on July 1st (top) and July 2nd (bottom) in Pinto landfill. The background shows the surface albedo observed during the campaign, and circle size and color both depict the emission rate.

The main areas at the landfill with emission sources in Las Dehasas are rather consistent between both airborne campaign dates. Most of the emissions arise from the southern part of the landfill, from what appears to be the active module of the facility. The 1st of July observations include two emission sources east of the module that are not present on July 2nd. After scrutinizing the exact methane fields associated to these two sources, it appears that the strongest of the two suffers from a source location discrepancy and is also associated with the module's active side. The other source, which is further away from the main cluster of sources, cannot be explained by such a discrepancy. Discussing these different locations with landfill operators could help shed a new light on these results.

Emission sources detected in Pinto are consistently spread along the full South-West – North-East axis of the landfill facility, for both airborne campaign days. Most of the sources have been observed on the southern flank of the landfill on July 1st, whereas most of them are on the northern flank on the next day. This result would need to be discussed with operators to examine if (shifts in) operational activities could explain it.

Besides airborne observations, GHGSat satellite data also allow us to visually pinpoint in which part of a facility plumes originate. Consequently, we have also visually evaluated the plume origins in all the satellite observations obtained from GHGSat. Figure 3-25 and Figure 3-26 compare these satellite plume sources with the sources observed during the airborne campaign for Las Dehasas and Pinto landfills, respectively.

Figure 3-25 Visual evaluation of the plume origins observed by GHGSat satellites above Las Dehasas (white crosses mark the individual plumes and the red shading depicts the estimated emission area) compared with sources locations observed during the airborne campaign (coloured circles) on July 1st (left) and July 2nd (right).

Figure 3-26 Visual evaluation of the plume origins observed by GHGSat satellites above Pinto (white crosses mark the individual plumes and the red shading depicts the estimated emission area) compared with sources locations observed during the airborne campaign (coloured circles) on July 1st (left) and July 2nd (right).

We find, for both Las Dehesas and Pinto, an overall consistency in the plume source locations between GHGSat satellite and airborne observations, even though the time period covered by the satellite observations is much longer. In Las Dehesas, satellite-observed plumes consistently originate from the southern section of the landfill from what appears to be the active module, consistent with the sources observed during the airborne campaign. In Pinto, both satellite- and airborne- observed plume sources are similarly scattered over the whole facility extent.

Optical Imager	Spatial Resolution [m]	Time period	Number of scenes analysed
Planet Labs	3.4	02/2022 – 09/2022	111
Sentinel 2	10	04/2018 – 06/2023	450
Maxar	0.5	04/2016 – 04/2023	10

Table 3-9 Summary of multispectral and optical imagery analysed over Madrid landfill sites.

Due to limited initial information on site operation and gas management from operators, efforts were made to use high resolution multispectral observations over 2018-2022 to discern site activity and identify active waste management cells. Data sets include Sentinel-2 (10m resolution, RGB, normalised differential vegetation index -NDVI, normalised differential water index - NDWI), Planet (3.4m resolution, RGB) and Maxar (< 1m resolution, RGB). Using Sentinel-2 we were able to identify the active cells of both Pinto and Las Dehesas, later identified by the site operators as Cell III at Pinto and Cells 7 (until Feb 2021) and 6 (2021-present) at Las Dehesas. Figure 3-27 displays GHGSat plume origin with respect to active cells of the Pinto and Las Dehesas facilities with currently active landfill regions depicted with white dotted lines and closed/completed cells

highlighted with red dotted lines. This active region analysis allowed us to confirm that the observed GHGSat plumes originated almost exclusively from the active or recently active cells, and not from the completed and fully capped older cells. This suggests that the active regions are the main source of fugitive methane, and that even recently completed cells such as Cell 7 are considerable sources of methane, despite degasification efforts

Figure 3-27 Active and inactive regions of Pinto and Las Dehesas identified from analysis of Sentinel-2, Planet and Maxar observations from 2018-2022, with GHGSat plume origins overlaid. Plume origins (white triangles) are provided by GHGSat.

We found Sentinel-2 NDVI particularly effective in identifying active waste management activities due to the elevated NDVI values of the waste in contrast with the dry soil/clay topped inactive cells. [RD-50] suggest such indices can be indicative of landfill change detection, waste removal and processing and monitoring presence of leachate. We analysed NDVI from Sentinel-2, in an attempt to correlate NDVI to site activity with the results shown in Figure 3-28, which captures both the NDVI over Cell 6 at Las Dehesas, as well as the area of NDVI pixels above a given threshold. The latter approach is successful in identifying the “clearing” phase of the cell, where the cell is stripped and prepared for waste, seen clearly by a dramatic drop in high NDVI pixels followed by a period of low values as the site is prepared. This is then followed by a variable NDVI as the cell enters operational use. In the TROPOMI record, we noticed higher more frequent enhancements over the sites during the winter and spring months. A potential driver of this is moisture, as increased levels of landfill leachate (water that has come into contact with landfill waste) often leads to increased levels of biogenic activity and thus, methane. These winter and spring months are when Spain sees the majority of its rainfall. Further work could include an investigation into the relationship between rainfall, leachate, temperature, NDVI, NDWI and the resultant levels of methane measured from satellite.

Proxies for activity: NDVI

Focusing on 2020-present active region

Figure 3-28 Investigating NDVI variations over the currently active cell (Cell 6) at Las Dehesas

3.4 CONCLUSIONS

3.4.1 SUMMARY

The overarching objective of this analysis was to conduct an intercomparison of methane concentrations and emissions from Sentinel-5p TROPOMI, GHGSat satellite data, and GHGSat aircraft observations over the area near Madrid, covering two landfills. For 2022, 10 GHGSat satellite observations and 2 days of GHGSat aircraft observations were provided for two landfill sites in the Madrid urban area, Pinto and Las Dehesas.

The GHGSat datasets were collocated with TROPOMI XCH₄ observations (using the operational (SRON) TROPOMI methane product and scientific methane product of WFMD TROPOMI) and, in the first part of our analysis, we performed intercomparisons of L2 TROPOMI pixels to resampled GHGSat satellite methane enhancements by spatially matching observations overpassing the Madrid area. We found good correlation between the GHGSat and TROPOMI enhancements ($R=0.86$), showing that strong plumes in GHGSat correspond to large enhancements in TROPOMI. Our TROPOMI minus resampled GHGSat satellite differences resulted in biases of 21.2 ppb and 10.1 ppb, for the operational TROPOMI and WFMD TROPOMI data products, respectively. The factors contributing to these differences include: a) the respective FOV differences between the TROPOMI and GHGSat sensors (GHGSat enhancements were integrated over a much larger pixel area effectively making the resampled GHGSat enhancements closer to zero), b) the fact that the plumes from the landfills drop below the GHGSat detection threshold at some point downwind of the source but still add to the enhancement seen with TROPOMI, c) TROPOMI enhancements also incorporate contributions from other point and diffuse emissions in the area, d) the time difference between the collocated TROPOMI and GHGSat data, meaning that the observations were not sampling the same air mass, and e) performing the intercomparisons in terms of methane enhancements rather than concentrations results in some discrepancies based on the background concentrations assumed to generate the methane enhancements.

Potentially more robust comparisons are expected when comparing the different measurements at emission level. TROPOMI emission estimates based on the operational and WFMD products, despite using different implementations of the IME method, showed consistent emission rates of 14 ± 9 (Operational) and 14 ± 8 (WFMD) t/hr. Considering their uncertainty, these values were similar to bottom-up values reported for Madrid by EDGAR and CAMS as well as consistent with – though higher than – previously reported values in the literature based on TROPOMI [RD-46]. The higher values may be the result of the fact that the IME method was only applied to days with plumes. A preliminary analytical inversion of TROPOMI data using the WRF model showed that emissions from the two landfills cannot be separated and that on individual days where the model accurately captured the transport in the area, the emission rates were similar to the IME results. For most days, mismatches in the transport and uncertainty in emissions elsewhere in the urban area warrant further work to accurately characterize the area's emissions. In general, the TROPOMI estimates are sensitive to a larger set of sources than just the two landfills, making comparing them to the GHGSat facility-level data difficult.

The GHGSat satellite emission data were rescaled using a landfill-specific calibration, resulting in average emissions rates of 2.5 ± 1.1 t/hr for Las Dehesas and 3.2 ± 1.7 t/hr for Pinto. Emissions from both facilities are remarkably strongly correlated ($r = 0.83$), hypotheses on this correlation are: similar operational constraints, similar meteorological

drivers, similar processing of the GHGSat observation as both landfills are captured in one scene. The latter two hypotheses were investigated but did not result in clear explanations of the correlation. The sum of the GHGSat aircraft plumes (after processing the data to prevent double-counting), was consistent with the GHGSat satellite data on the day with overlapping data (July 1st, 1.6 ± 0.4 (airborne) versus 2.3 ± 1.3 t/hr for Las Dehesas and 2.4 ± 0.3 (airborne) versus 2.3 ± 1.3 t/hr for Pinto). GHGSat data show significantly larger emissions than reported to E-PRTR by both Las Dehesas (0.3 t/hr) and Pinto (1.6 t/hr), a difference that remains when using a different calibration on the satellite data. Based on an exchange with the Las Dehesas landfill operator, the reported emissions are a function of the assumed gas capture efficiency of the landfill. The results therefore suggest that the capture efficiency may be overestimated, something that has also been reported in the literature for landfills in the US [RD-47].

We have seen that GHGSat airborne observation allow the identification of a lot of individual sources within the landfill. These identifications can be used to mitigate emissions if promptly communicated to the landfill operator. The locations of these sources were consistent with the overall sources found based on the GHGSat satellite data. Activity was concentrated in active areas of the landfills that were also identified by analyzing space-based visual and NDVI/NDWI imagery from Sentinel-2, Planet, and Maxar.

3.4.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Our analysis of methane emission rates for the Madrid landfill sites using a range of methods (area flux mappers, point source mappers and model inversions) has highlighted that there are some differences observed with the emissions reported to the European Commission. With specific reference to the recent GHGSat aircraft campaign conducted in 2022, the TROPOMI and GHGSat satellite emission estimates, and engagement with the Las Dehesas site operators (21st July 2022), we list a series of recommendations below which would further support our understanding of the factors driving the observed emissions and aim to bridge the gap with facility-reported emission. We split our recommendations between general recommendations (including further analysis of existing data) and recommendations for future campaigns.

General recommendations:

- Conduct an additional analysis of GHGSat satellite plume features and emissions timeseries to include observations captured prior to the 2022 field campaign and more recent observations until the present day.
- Ground-based surveying using network of sensors to capture surface fluxes/total column concentrations (i.e., EM-27 spectrometers) for direct inter-comparison with satellite XCH₄ total columns and fluxes, and on-site Optical Gas Imaging campaigns.
- Inter-comparison of meteorological databases with the public weather station data used for on-site meteorological information and collection of dedicated new on-site meteorological information.
- Improving the analysis of Madrid city-area emissions based on TROPOMI data and atmospheric inversion using WRF, including accounting for transport errors and spatial errors in bottom-up inventories.
- Begin engagement with Pinto landfill site to understand management and facility operations to add context to observed emissions by GHGSat.
- Further interact with (both) landfill operators to discuss:
 - Plume origins compared to on-site operations.
 - Facility-level bottom-up estimates comparisons (decay models, biogas collection efficiency ratio, etc) with field campaign results and airborne + satellite observations.
 - Further compare and reconcile to suborbital and surface observations, including those done at the landfill. Possibly aided with on-site meteorological data.

Recommendations for future campaigns:

- Extend the satellite and airborne observation time series to better understand the variability and potential drivers of methane emissions, as well as to evaluate methane emission quantification in a broader set of atmospheric and operational conditions.
- Additional dedicated GHGSat (and MAMAP) aircraft campaign coinciding more directly with GHGSat and TROPOMI satellite overpass times.
- Additional ground-based measurements included in the campaign to intercompare methods. For example, including downwind measurements that estimate emissions using a dual-tracer approach where a trace gas is released on the landfill to improve the emission quantification.
- Have quicker feedback to the operator during future aircraft campaigns to be able to connect detected plumes to activities or leaks present at the landfill at that moment in time.

4. DETAILED VALIDATION – POLAND COALMINES

This report focusses on methane (CH₄) emissions from Polish coalmines, following on from EDAP+ TN on GHGSat validation part A which focussed primarily on investigating CH₄ emissions from Madrid landfill with Sentinel 5p TROPOMI and GHGSat observations. Analysis of TROPOMI data indicated a large CH₄ hotspot over Southern Poland, coinciding with large presence of coal mines in Silesian region. Additional interrogation of the European Emission and Pollutant Register (E-PRTR) indicates that Poland comprises of the top 10 emitting coal mines (282,300 tonnes of CH₄) in Europe with the largest cluster of coal mines located in the Silesian region. Typically, for underground coal mines, large-scale ventilation systems are used to provide the flow of fresh air underground to help dilute gases such as methane, as well as help regulate the temperature for safe working conditions. However, this ‘ventilation air methane’ ultimately ends up being released into the atmosphere, thereby acting as a source of fugitive methane.

In this report, we present our analysis of CH₄ enhancements and emissions using TROPOMI from January 2018 to August 2022 and GHGSat satellite observations from June 2022 to August 2022. We focussed on the hotspot region which contains clusters of coal mines (with as much as 23 sites in operation at one point) in the Upper Silesia Coalmine Basin (USCB). In the case of TROPOMI, data coverage over the USCB was often sparse and incomplete due to a large proportion of missing data pixels compared to Madrid. This is most likely due to increased cloud coverage and lower albedo at these latitudes. Using the Integrated Mass Enhancement (IME) method we calculated emissions of $32,525 \pm 8,927$ kg/hr for the period between 2018 and 2022. Due to incomplete data coverage in a large proportion of TROPOMI orbits analysed, these estimates represent only selected regions of the USCB, capturing emissions from only some coalmines, and for a particular snapshot in time. The GHGSat satellite observations between June and August 2022 yielded an average CH₄ emission over the USCB region of 4050 ± 2050 kg/hr over individual coal mine facilities and much like TROPOMI, only represent selected coalmines from selected parts of the USCB.

We conducted an initial investigation of the reported emissions to the European emission and pollutant register (E-PRTR) from these coal mines, and additional emissions calculated by the Copernicus global anthropogenic emission inventory. We found that emissions reported to E-PRTR were more than 4x larger than those calculated by GHGSat and Copernicus emissions were 2x larger than those calculated from TROPOMI. A key reason for these discrepancies was due to the incomplete data coverage or selective targeting from the satellites over the USCB region and as such, it is important to note that TROPOMI and GHGSat emissions do not represent the entire basin. A key consistency we found was that the largest emissions were observed in the south-west region of USCB in both TROPOMI and GHGSat satellite datasets, and in the Copernicus inventory. This particular area comprises a large cluster of underground mines and ventilation shafts and the satellite observations from TROPOMI and GHGSat confirm that this the primary region of large CH₄ enhancements.

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4.1 INTRODUCTION

The coal mining industry contributes significantly to global methane emissions and is responsible for around 33% of all fossil fuel related emissions of methane from 2008 to 2017 (RD-54). Typically, for underground coal mines, large-scale ventilation systems are used to provide the flow of fresh air underground to help dilute gases such as methane, as well as help regulate the temperature for safe working conditions. However, this ‘ventilation air methane’ ultimately ends up being released into the atmosphere, thereby acting as a source of fugitive methane. According to the European Commission and the European Environment Agency, the top 10 largest methane emitting coal mines in Europe are in Poland. Collectively, these mines released around 282 kilo tonnes of methane into the atmosphere in 2020 [RD-43]. On 21st March 2022, ESA released a web story reporting the detection of enhanced methane concentrations from a cluster of coal mines in Poland, highlighting work carried out by the University of Leicester. Using wind-rotated and averaged TROPOMI XCH₄ data between 2018 and 2020, the accumulated methane signal over Poland was calculated and revealed that the largest concentrations over the Upper Silesian Coal Basin (Figure 4-1), west of Krakow, a prominent mining region dominated by a cluster of underground coal mines.

Figure 4-1 Methane concentration anomaly above coal mines in Poland, measured from TROPOMI, data product from University of Bremen, processed by University of Leicester.

This article followed a prior web story, referenced previously, concerning methane emissions from landfill in Madrid, Spain. As with Madrid, ESA procured 10 days of GHGSat methane observations over these coal mines during a summer 2022 aircraft campaign, and whilst Madrid took priority in the EDAP+ GHGSat validation study, results of the Poland analysis are presented here.

4.2 MEASUREMENTS

4.2.1 TROPOMI SATELLITE DATA

As described in section 3.1.2 of this document (Part 1), we analysed XCH₄ data from the WFMD TROPOMI V1.8 L2 data product and focussed on the time period of January 2018

to August 2022. Using these data, we extracted TROPOMI overpasses for Poland and calculated CH₄ emissions using the IME method described in section 3.2.1.1.

4.2.2 GHGSat SATELLITE DATA

Similar to the Madrid campaign, 10 GHGSat satellite observations were procured over a period of 2 months from 2022-06-11 to 2022-08-05. Table 4-1 and *Figure 4-2* present the details of these observations. The separation of the targeted coal mines from one another presents an additional challenge, as not every coal mine is included in the 12 km GHGSat swath. Therefore, we cannot compare emissions from different mines for the same day, as only a handful of sites are covered in each overpass. Additionally, this also means that of the 10 observations, no coalmine regions were revisited more than twice. To accompany the satellite observations, GHGSat aircraft measurements were also made on the 20th July and 24th July 2022, however these have not been analysed in this part of the study.

Date	Satellite name	Observation ID	Number of detected plumes
2022-06-11	C3	DZ11TQT	2
2022-06-15	C1	7Zp0t54	2
2022-06-18	C4	HZs1Jtl	5
2022-06-19	C3	DZt1O54	7
2022-06-29	C3	D_32bKv	2
2022-06-30	C3	D_41O54	5
2022-07-25	C5	L_QEotl	3
2022-08-04	C3	D_b3fqt	4
2022-08-05	C3	D_c2fqt	3
2022-08-12	C5	L_j3KoK	2

Table 4-1 Summary of 10 GHGSat satellite observations obtained over Poland.

Figure 4-2 shows the range of CH₄ emissions captured over various coalmines in the Silesian mining region of Poland with GHGSat satellite observations targeting 13 coal mines. Emissions reported by GHGSat vary from 1827 kg/hr to 15755 kg/hr collectively for various sites. Some interesting features worth noting are that on some days, such as 11th June 2022, observed plumes followed different wind directions despite being on a few kilometres from each other in location. Additionally, the largest emissions (exceeding 15,000 kg/hr) were captured on the 19th June 2022 with plumes observed in the south-west region of the Silesian mining area where a number of underground mines are located. Emissions over these sites dropped slightly (close to 10,000 kg/hr) ten days later suggesting that this area may dominate the emission signals observed in this region.

GHGSat observations over Poland

Figure 4-2 Overview of the observations procured from GHGSat of methane enhancements above the Poland coalmines. Orange colours represent the CH₄ concentration enhancement and white triangles represent the plume origin as calculated by GHGSat.

4.3 TROPOMI – GHGSat Intercomparisons

Using the methodology stated in section 3.1.1, GHGSat observations were resampled to the TROPOMI pixel grid, as done with Madrid, following the same process. Only two overpasses had TROPOMI pixels within the domain of the GHGSat plumes, limiting the analysis. The two successful scenarios are presented in *Figure 4-3* and show poor correlation between the two instruments, likely due to the same issues faced with Madrid. Namely: different overpass time, different sensitivity to spatial scales, changing wind fields and changing emissions. The observed differences in terms of CH₄ enhancement were as

high as 29.0 ppb with TROPOMI observed to be 98 % larger than the resampled GHGSat data.

Figure 4-3 Two successful GHGSat measurements resampled to the pixel grid of TROPOMI, with enhancements compared for co-incident pixels, conducted with only GHGSat pixels that are contained within the plume mask provided by GHGSat.

4.4 TROPOMI Emission Quantification

To analyse coal mining regions in Poland with TROPOMI, we defined a Poland domain that encompassed all the sites covered by the GHGSat observations as displayed in the pink box in *Figure 4-4* (left) with coordinates 48, 53.5, -15.5, 26.5 (minimum latitude, maximum latitude, minimum longitude, maximum longitude respectively). However, as the figure shows, the coalmines fall into two distinct areas: one where they are clustered together towards the west of the domain (*Figure 4-4* middle) and an isolated coalmine towards the east of the domain (*Figure 4-4* right). For this study, we focussed on the coalmine cluster located in the Upper Silesian Coal Basin (USCB) located in the south-west region of Poland.

Figure 4-4 Left: Poland domain, areas of interest (AOI) and coalmine site locations; Middle: Zoom into cluster of Poland coalmine sites within the USCB region; Right: Zoom into isolated Poland coalmine in the east of the domain.

Considering the coarse spatial resolution of TROPOMI pixels and the close proximity in terms of distance between many of the Silesian coalmines (only a few km in some cases), attributing emissions to a specific coalmine was not possible as 1 TROPOMI pixel could capture signatures from several coalmines. Therefore, we separated the clusters of Silesian coalmines into 4 sectors to attribute emissions in sector of the USCB coalmining region instead. Table 4-2 shows the corresponding coalmine ID (using a list provided by the GHGSat team) and lists which sector of the USCB region the mine falls into. These sites were selected by analysing the top emitting coal mines in Poland according to [RD-43]. Note that each coal mine targeted may have more than 1 ventilation shaft from which CH₄ can be dispersed into the atmosphere. The Silesian coalmine sites targeted in this study and their respective latitude and longitude locations, as well as sector we place them in, can be seen in *Figure 4-5*.

Figure 4-5 Map of the Silesian coalmine locations with their ID number and their corresponding sector (1, 2, 3 or 4).

Coal mine ID	Latitude	Longitude	Sector	Description
1	49.93317	19.01037	4	POL-AV_S22_3-WM
2	50.04878	18.46285	3	POL-AV_S22_1-WM
3	50.19516	18.65872	1	POL-SL_CMI_Target2_Underg_Mine-MN-UGD
4	49.98582	18.62001	3	POL-SL_CMI_Target3_Underg_Mine-MN-UGD
5	49.9949	19.1051	4	POL-Gilowice-OG-MPI
6	49.9419	19.0131	4	EU_-_PL_-_Silesia-coal-mine-2014-24p3Kt
7	50.19962	19.04024	2	POL-AV_S22_4-WM
8	49.96971	18.71004	3	POL-AV_S22_2-WM
9	50.21	19.085	2	POL-Silesian_Coal_Mine_S3-MN-UGD
10	49.9869	19.1556	4	EU_-_PL_-_Brzeszcze-coal-mine—2014-39Kt
11	49.9672	18.6897	3	EU_-_PL_-_Pniowek-Coal-mine_2014-62Kt
12	50.0455	18.5884	3	POL_SL-KWK_Row_Coal_Mine-Underg_Mine
13	50.2219	18.6721	1	POL_SL-JSW_Coal_Mines-Underg_Mine

Table 4-2 Silesian coalmines ID number corresponding to the map on Figure 4-5, with their latitude and longitude coordinates, sector number and description.

As with the Madrid study, the same approaches to handling, processing and analysing the TROPOMI WFMD XCH₄ data and ERA-5 wind fields were taken (see section 3.2.1.1 of this document). There were much fewer high-quality plumes detected over the coal mines compared to the Madrid landfills, due to poorer data coverage.

4.4.1 TROPOMI OBSERVATIONS

Overall TROPOMI coverage over the Polish coal mines was not as complete as that observed over Madrid, with only 10.7% of the TROPOMI orbits having reasonable data coverage over Sectors 1-4. Following the plume masking process, only 4.9 % of observations had successful high-confidence CH₄ plumes. Similar to the Madrid landfill

sites, the Silesian coalmines show a seasonal cycle in terms of average XCH_4 and an ascending trend (see *Figure 4-6 top*). The wind characterisation (*Figure 4-6 bottom*) for the Silesian coalmines wind speeds between 0.5 m/s and 9.5 m/s (average close to 4 m/s) and generally show higher wind speeds than those observed in Madrid.

Figure 4-6 Time series of the mean (μ) \pm standard deviation (σ) over the Silesian coalmine sites AOI for all available L3u data. Bremen preliminary data v1.8T period is shaded in grey. Top: XCH_4 ; Bottom: Local wind speed at closest overpass hour.

4.5 TROPOMI EMISSIONS

Using the persistent anomaly detection method described in section 3.2.1.1 of this document, we defined an AOI for USCB region as shown in *Figure 4-7* to identify the hotspot where CH_4 enhancements are most prominent. *Figure 4-7* shows that the largest concentration of CH_4 enhancements is focussed on the centre of the AOI where each of the selected coal mines are also shown (coloured circles). A notable difference to the Madrid case is that there is a much larger proportion of missing data (indicated by white spaces) over South Poland likely due to increased cloud coverage and weaker albedo at this latitude. *Figure 4-7* also indicates the largest hotspots occur in our defined sectors 1 (coal mine IDs 3 & 13) in the north-west corner and 3 (coal mine IDs 2,4,8,11 & 12) in the south-west corner of the Silesian mining region.

Figure 4-7 Hotspot map showing the normalised number of days with XCH₄ anomalies for the Bremen L3u data within the AOI of the Poland Silesian coalmines, with the location of the study sites as coloured circles.

Despite the less-than-ideal TROPOMI coverage over the Poland AOI, we applied the IME method to calculate emissions for each sector of the USCB region. *Figure 4-8* shows examples of TROPOMI orbits for several days and the corresponding plume masks calculated over for some of the sectors in the USCB region. These maps illustrate that on individual days, TROPOMI data coverage can contain large gaps within the pixels meaning that generating a complete plume mask is challenging and sometimes the “observed” plume, although integrated, may not resemble an expected plume shape. In other cases, observed enhancements did not show continuous features or overlap with the defined sectors in which case, these orbits were removed from analysis as these conditions made it difficult to attribute the emissions to a particular sector.

Figure 4-8 Poland Silesian coalmines for a range of days from 2018 to 2021. For each date, there are 3 maps that correspond to the following; left: TROPOMI CH₄ enhancement map with wind vectors; middle: corresponding plume mask using the threshold; right: corresponding plume mask for the IME method using DBSCAN attributed.

To calculate CH₄ emissions for the USCB region, we applied the IME method to each sector (1,2,3 & 4) within each orbit analysed. The IME did not always yield a successful plume mask for each of the sectors analysed in which case, we were not able to report the total CH₄ emissions for USCB region but instead we only report the emission for each sector that resulted in a successful emission calculation. *Figure 4-9* shows the range of CH₄ emissions calculated from January 2018 to August 2022 with only 21 emission estimates captured.

Figure 4-9 Emission rates and error bars in kg/h time series for selected TROPOMI Bremen data over Poland Silesian coalmines AOI. Estimated using the IME method and DBSCAN plume masking, coloured by sector plume origin with symbol indicating wind speed conditions.

Figure 4-9 shows a predominance of successfully captured plumes for sector 3 (shown in pink), an absence of plumes found in 2019, and a majority of overpasses with wind speeds higher than 2 m/s. The higher number of persistent features in sector 3 could be due to the larger clustering of coalmines, where we know that 2 out of the 5 mines targeted by

GHGSat are underground coalmines (see Table 4-2). Underground coalmines could emit more due to venting, and this explanation is consistent with the emissions observed over sector 1 (the second most persistent sector) where 2 out of 2 of its coalmines are underground. Even though sector 4 encompasses 4 coalmines, there is no indication in their description of any being underground. However, there could be other influencing factors such as predominant wind direction going south-west which means that more plumes can be attributed to sector 3 only following the wind direction. [RD-48] confirms that the USCB in the Silesian Upland has a predominant south-west wind. Another factor could be the landscape, which could be favouring more data coverage in sector 3.

The lowest emission rates observed generally have wind speeds lower than 2 m/s. The emission rates are consistent with those that capture the largest plume area and average CH₄ enhancements. Overall, there is a wide range of emissions observed over each sector of the USCB region ranging from 5000 kg/h to 60000 kg/h.

Using the Methane Air-borne MAPper (MAMAP) instrument and cross-sectional method to calculate emissions, [RD-52] defined coalmine clusters in the USCB similar to the ones we defined in this study (see Figure 4-10) which are equivalent to our USCB “sectors”. Their “cluster b” comprises seven ventilation shafts from the three mines Pniówek (3), Zofiówka (2), and Borynia (2) and is equivalent to our sector 3, for which they also have the most comprehensive collection of measurements out of the 4 clusters they study. Their wind speeds, derived from wind lidar stations, were generally around 5 to 6 m/s and dropped to around 2 m/s in “cluster b” similarly to the ones acquired in our study from ERA5 (from 1.4 to 4.8 m/s for sector 3). Based on one single overflight on the 28th May 2018 capturing all mines in their “cluster b”, they report emissions of 10400 kg/h with a 26% emission error. This estimate is similar to our lowest CH₄ emission for sector 3 on the 31st March 2021 of 14877.2 kg/h with a 19.4% emission error. These estimates also agree well with the reported emissions for cluster b of 12600 kg/h from the CoMet ED v4 inventory for the year 2018.

Regarding the other sectors, they estimated fluxes for “cluster a” (our sector 1) of 1600 kg/h in average whereas we estimate 10 times more emissions with at least ~16000 kg/h. For “cluster c” (our sector 4) they report 2800 kg/h for a single overflight which is half of what we estimate for a single overpass on the 13th October 2018 with 5825.5 kg/h. Finally, for cluster d (our sector 2), their average estimate is the highest of these three clusters with 7600 kg/h but still much lower to our estimates of ~40000 kg/h.

Figure 4-10 Fig. 2 from [RD-52], with description, showing the USCB region with CoMet ED v4 inventory emissions as reported in 2018. In this figure, active coal mine ventilation shafts are indicated by blue triangles and the colour intensity reflects the annual CH₄ emission according to CoMET ED v4 inventory for 2018. Note that the region is split into 4 clusters which are equivalent to the sectors used in this study and in cluster b (equivalent to sector 3 in this study), a total of 6 mine shafts were targeted.

Overall, from 2018 to 2021, using TROPOMI WFMD XCH₄ data, we calculated an average emission of 32,525 kg/hr ± 8,927 kg/hr for the Poland Silesian coalmines. These emission rates only represent the total of all USCB sectors analysed for those TROPOMI orbits where the IME successfully yielded a plume mask and emission rate. With this in mind, some caution needs to be exercised when using these emission estimates as they are based on incomplete data coverage which does not represent an even distribution across the entire USCB region. There were no successfully masked plumes from TROPOMI coinciding with the GHGSat satellite observations and for this reason, there could not be a comparison between both instruments in this location.

In order to put these emissions into context, we conducted a comparison to the Copernicus anthropogenic methane emission inventory (CAMS_GLOB_ANT_v4.2) using the emission estimates for 2020. Within the USCB domain, fugitives, solid waste disposal, agricultural livestock, residential & commercial, and industrial processes are top 5 contributing sources of CH₄ emissions in the area. *Figure 4-11* displays a timeseries of these emission sources within the USCB AOI and shows that whilst fugitives dominate in terms of emissions, there are sizable contributions from the agricultural livestock, solid waste disposal, and residential & commercial sectors. To extract the CH₄ emissions of most relevance to the coal mining sector we extracted the annual emissions defined as fugitives and industrial processes which come to a combined total of 77,800 kg/hr. This value is double that calculated from TROPOMI and reflects the limitations, mainly the sparse data coverage and the inconsistent sampling of the 4 USCB sectors, in the TROPOMI emission calculations over this region.

Figure 4-11 Timeseries of CH₄ emissions from the Copernicus anthropogenic methane emissions inventory for 2020 as estimated for a range of anthropogenic sources located in the USCB region.

Figure 4-12 Spatial map showing the CH₄ emissions for fugitive sources, in units of kg/hr, for the USCB region. Red dots represent the positions of the 13 coal mines listed in Table 4-2.

Figure 4-12 shows the CAMS CH₄ fugitive emissions for the USCB region and highlights that the largest emissions even within the CAMS inventory occur over USCB sector 3. Fugitive emissions mainly refer to gas venting and flaring of coalbed CH₄ during underground or surface coal mining according to the EDGARv4.3.2 inventory [RD-53] and this is consistent with the higher number of underground coalmines in sector 3.

4.6 GHGSat Emissions

Figure 4-13 shows the total emissions captured during the 10 days of GHGSat satellite observations collected over the 13 coal mines during the months of June to August 2022. There are several caveats to note when interpreting this figure; firstly, the total emissions only represent the selected coal mines targeted on that day, and secondly, the total emissions shown do not represent the entire USCB region and therefore these emissions only represent a snapshot in time and coverage. The total emission calculated for all coal mines within the USCB region as reported to the E-PRTR in 2021 shows emission total at 23,268kg/hr (based on reporting from 12 coal mines) which is larger than those reported in GHGSat, however the reasons for this difference is noted in the caveats listed above.

Figure 4-13 Emissions quantified from GHGSat satellite observations, as provided by individual GHGSat and summed for each day. The annual emissions reported by the coal mine industry to E-PRTR are also shown (grey line) as are emissions calculated by the Copernicus anthropogenic emission inventory (green line). Note, that the GHGSat observations do not target the same coal mine day to day.

We conducted an investigation of the coal mining emissions reported to E-PRTR for the USCB region and the total emissions for Poland USCB mining operations since 2008 are shown in *Figure 4-14*. A notable feature in this figure is that there is a significant drop from 410 kT to 200 kT between 2016 and 2017 with reported emissions almost halving, and remaining close to 200 kT until 2021. *Figure 4-15* shows the E-PRTR emissions for 2016 and 2017 spatially and highlights that the number of mining operators reporting their CH₄ emissions to E-PRTR in the Silesian region have dropped from 22 mines in 2016 to 12 mines in 2017. It is possible that some mining sites were closed post-2016 and media reports suggested that some mines were to be closed down through an agreement between the European Commission and the Polish government [RD-55]. However, investigation into the USCB region using the Global Coal Mine Tracker from the Global Energy Monitor organisation (<https://globalenergymonitor.org/about/>) suggests that there are still close to 20 mines in operation in the Silesian region. It is possible that some companies have taken over and merged several mining sites (see <https://www.noerr.com/en/insights/agreement-on-establishment-of-polish-mining-group-signed>) but this does not explain why the reported emissions are lower than those observed in 2016 and currently, we do not know if this is because sites are no longer in operation, or there has been some reduction in emission due to facility processes. It should be further noted that the emissions from E-PRTR (24,000 kg/hr) for 2021 are lower than those estimated from the annual CAMS fugitive emissions (77 kg/hr) for 2020. These discrepancies would need to be further investigated in follow on work.

Figure 4-14 CH₄ emissions from underground/overground mining operations from the Poland Silesian mining region as reported to the EPRTR.

Figure 4-15 Spatial map of Poland Silesian mining operation EPRTR emissions for 2016 (left) and 2017 (right).

4.7 CONCLUSIONS

4.7.1 SUMMARY

In this investigation, we focussed on the Silesian coal mining region in Southern Poland using GHGSat and TROPOMI satellite observations to estimate coal mining CH₄ emissions. Using TROPOMI WFMD XCH₄ data from Jan 2018 to Aug 2022 and 10 days of GHGSat observations, we calculated emissions for selected coal mines and performed an intercomparison between GHGSat and TROPOMI CH₄ enhancements.

Out of 13 coal mines targeted by the GHGSat satellite observations, not all mines were captured on each day and therefore repeat measurements and calculated emission estimates were not available for every single mine. For TROPOMI orbits, we often found insufficient data coverage over Poland likely owing to cloud coverage and low albedo scenes which meant that successful plume masking was challenging. This was particularly difficult when scenes over Poland had large gaps or missing data; this proved to be a limitation in identifying large numbers of scenes with full complete plumes (i.e. without missing pixels). Another challenge was that some mines were in close proximity to each other (a few km's) meaning that individual plume isolation would be difficult and to counteract this, we split the Silesian mining region into 4 sectors. The IME method was applied each of these 4 sectors using individual orbit data between Jan 2018 and Aug 2022 and for successful plumes, CH₄ emissions were calculated. Out of the 943 TROPOMI orbits analysed, only 21 yielded successful emission calculations which averaged at 32,525 kg/hr \pm 8927 kg/hr representing only a snapshot of the emissions over the Silesian mining region for only a selection of mines. The largest emissions were captured in the south-west region of the Silesian mining region. For 2020, CAMS anthropogenic emission inventory estimates fugitive emissions from the coal mining industry at 77,000 kg/hr which is almost double that estimated from TROPOMI. Whilst our TROPOMI emission estimates are limited by lack of adequate data coverage, one way to disentangle these emissions contributions would be to conduct WRF modelling for the USCB region.

For GHGSat, the observations captured plumes from individual coal mines due to the finer spatial resolution of the GHGSat footprint compared to TROPOMI, however not all coal mines were targeted on each day. Similar to the case for TROPOMI, this meant that the GHGSat emission estimates do not represent the entire Silesian mining basin, but instead provide a snapshot of emissions related only to some mines. Between June and August 2022, GHGSat observed emissions of 4050 \pm 2050 kg/hr. This is lower than the 23,000 kg/hr reported by the E-PRTR database for 2021 which represents the cumulative emissions for all mines in the Silesian mining basin whereas the GHGSat emissions total represents only selected mines. This is in contrast to the Madrid case, where GHGSat was found to be 3x larger than the E-PRTR emissions for the landfills. Clearly, further site-specific investigation. It should be noted that mines located in the southwest region of the USCB yielded larger CH₄ emissions which is consistent with the results found for TROPOMI and by [RD-52] using MAMAP aircraft observations.

Overall, care must be taken when interpreting these emissions from TROPOMI and GHGSat, because they do not represent the cumulative emissions of the entire basin but rather snapshots in time and for selected mines.

4.7.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to unpick some of the differences observed, some recommendations are proposed in follow-on projects:

- Further interrogation of GHGSat aircraft plumes and emissions
- Capturing a longer timeseries of observations of *all* mines area in Poland with GHGSat to understand the emissions related to the entire Silesian basin. If this is not possible, then focussing on the southwest region of the Silesian basin would be useful as this is the region where TROPOMI, GHGSat, and the CAMS inventory capture the largest emissions.
- Further interrogation of GHGSat plumes with specific coal mining operations, to better evaluate individual site performance vs. reported emission inventories.
- Conducting intercomparisons of different emission inventories such as Copernicus anthropogenic methane emissions database or EDGAR and dedicated USCB WRF modelling with these emission inventories.
- It would be useful to contact some of the mine operators for clarification as to whether certain sites have closed post-2016 and to better evidence the drop in reported CH₄ emissions to E-PRTR.

5. MISSION TEST DATASET

5.1 GHGSat

For this study, 10 satellite observations in 2022 have been obtained to GHGSat over Madrid landfills, at dates matching clear sky coverage for TROPOMI observations.

For each observation, the deliverable includes a set of files providing retrieval results at pixel-level for albedo, methane concentration enhancement, methane uncertainty, and quality flag.

Date	Satellite name	Observation ID
2022-02-28	C2	AY-1E_Z
2022-03-01	C2	AYA1E_Z
2022-04-03	C2	AYf8j_Z
2022-05-06	C2	AZC1E_Z
2022-05-31	C2	AZa1yUz
2022-06-05	C1	7ZeATUz
2022-06-27	C1	7ZyLyUz
2022-07-01	C2	A_52TUz
2022-07-08	C1	7_B2TUz
2022-07-31	C1	7_X8yUz

Table here below summarizes the GHGSat aircraft observation per landfill facility and per airborne campaign day.

Date	Landfill	Number of frames	Number of detected plumes	Number of overpasses
2022-07-01	Pinto	28	57	4
	Las Dehesas	21	16	6
2022-07-02	Pinto	42	37	5
	Las Dehesas	27	34	6

For this study, 10 satellite observations in 2022 have been obtained to GHGSat over Poland mines, at dates matching clear sky coverage for TROPOMI observations.

Date	Satellite name	Observation ID
2022-06-11	C3	DZI1TQT
2022-06-15	C1	7Zp0t54
2022-06-18	C4	HZs1Jtl
2022-06-19	C3	DZt1O54
2022-06-29	C3	D_32bKv
2022-06-30	C3	D_41O54
2022-07-25	C5	L_QEotl
2022-08-04	C3	D_b3fqt
2022-08-05	C3	D_c2fqt
2022-08-12	C5	L_j3KoK

5.2 TROPOMI

List of the 45 orbits selected for IME quantification using the operational TROPOMI XCH4 product:

21893, 21936, 22007, 22063, 22077, 22120, 22262, 22290, 22319, 22418, 22574, 22588, 23482, 23624, 23936, 23950, 23993, 24390, 24433, 24532, 24546, 24617, 24702, 24844, 24872, 24901, 24972, 25128, 25142, 25156, 25213, 25227, 25312, 25582, 25610, 25681, 25837, 26234, 26249, 26263, 26575, 26958, 26972, 26986, 27029

List of orbits (January to August 2022) selected for IME quantification with IUP WFMD TROPOMI XCH4 data products:

22021, 22049, 22106, 22134, 22148, 22149, 22247, 22248, 22262, 22276, 22404, 22418, 22574, 22588, 23212, 23213, 23340, 23468, 23624, 23638, 23695, 23780, 23922, 23936, 23950, 23993, 24092, 24149, 24333, 24334, 24390, 24432, 24433, 24461, 24475, 24532, 24617, 24631, 24659, 24660, 24744, 24745, 24759, 24815, 24816, 24844, 24858, 24872, 24873, 24901, 24915, 24929, 24972, 24986, 25057, 25071, 25085, 25113, 25114, 25128, 25142, 25156, 25227

5.3 ERA wind fields

Figure 5-1 Comparison of ERA 5 land and ERA 5 single level at TROPOMI and GHGSat overpass times on the 8th July 2022.

5.4 WFMD TROPOMI methane emissions

Figure 5-2 Comparison of emission rate estimates obtained from IUP WFMD TROPOMI XCH4 data for Madrid urban area in 2022 (January to August). Emissions reported with GHGSat satellite (blue) and aircraft (red) observations are shown. For comparison, also plotted are the E-PRTR emissions for 2021 (grey line), mean and standard deviation of emission estimates from operational TROPOMI IME processed by SRON (magenta solid and dotted lines), and mean emissions from WRF inversion with EDGAR (light blue line) and CAMS (green line) processed by SRON.

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